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**Search for the charged Higgs boson
using the CMS Detector**

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Acknowledgements

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Resumo

Este texto descreve os resultados da Pesquisa de bósons de Higgs carregados em decaimentos de pares de quarks top-antitop no detector CMS.

Palavras-chave: Higgs, top, ttbar, tau, MSSM

Abstract

This text presents the results on the search for the charged Higgs boson in top-antitop quark pair decays using the CMS detector.

The Higgs Mechanism needs at least one Higgs doublet to allow particles to have mass in the Standard Model. However, there is no fundamental reason to exist just one Higgs doublet. With two Higgs doublets, after symmetry breaking, there is a pair of charged Higgs bosons (conjugates of each other). These charged Higgs bosons may be produced in top quark decays. Supersymmetry requires at least two Higgs doublets.

The work was developed within the LIP-CMS group at Lisbon, the Higgs to 2 taus CMS sub-group and the Higgs CMS group from June 2009 until September 2010. Two scenarios predicted by the Minimal Supersymmetric extension to the Standard Model are considered: the charged Higgs decays exclusively to a tau lepton and a neutrino, the charged Higgs decays exclusively to charm and anti-strange quarks.

A preliminary study based on Monte Carlo Simulation at 10TeV of top-antitop quarks pair decays in the Minimal Supersymmetric extension to the Standard Model was done. Then, twenty exclusive categories of events were defined and the Profile Likelihood method was used to extract exclusion limits at 95% CL for the Branching Ratio of the top quark decay to charged Higgs and bottom quark from $2pb^{-1}$ of data. Projections for the results obtained with more data are also shown. The current Branching Ratio exclusion limits, from Tevatron, may be improved with around $10pb^{-1}$ of data.

The first chapter contains an introduction to top quark, charged Higgs and tau decays. The second chapter contains an introduction to the CMS experiment. The third chapter describes the preliminary study at 10TeV based on Monte Carlo Simulation. The fourth chapter describes the study at 7TeV, the first results from data and the projections. The last chapter contains the conclusions and the perspectives for larger integrated luminosities.

Keywords: Higgs, top, ttbar, tau, MSSM

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Acronyms

SM Standard Model of Particle Physics

2HDM Two Higgs Doublets Models

MSSM Minimal Supersymmetric extension to the Standard Model

$\tan\beta$ the ratio of the vacuum expectation values of the two Higgs doublets

H^+ charged Higgs boson

$\text{BR}(t \rightarrow H^+b)$ branching ratio of the decay of the top quark to a charged Higgs boson and a bottom quark

$\text{BR}(H^+ \rightarrow \tau^+\nu_\tau)$ branching ratio of the decay of the charged Higgs boson to an anti tau lepton and a tau neutrino

$\text{BR}(H^+ \rightarrow c\bar{s})$ branching ratio of the decay of the charged Higgs boson to a charm and an anti strange quarks

$q\bar{q}$ quark antiquark pair

$t\bar{t}$ top antitop quark pair

pp proton-proton

$p\bar{p}$ proton-antiproton

jet narrow cone of hadrons and other particles produced by the hadronization of a quark or gluon with high momentum

p_T Momentum transverse to the proton beams axis

$|\eta|$ Absolute value of the pseudo-rapidity

\cancel{E}_T Missing energy transverse to the proton beams axis

Tevatron Tevatron Collider

LHC Large Hadron Collider

LIP Laboratory of Instrumentation and Experimental Particle Physics

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Top quark

Particle physics is a branch of physics that studies the elementary subatomic constituents of matter and radiation, and the interactive relationship between them. The top quark is an elementary particle. It is a fermion with an electric charge of $+2/3e$ and it is the most massive of all observed elementary particles, it has a mass of $172 \pm 2 GeV/c^2$ [3].

Figure 1.1: Leading order Feynman diagrams for single top quark production. Approximate cross sections for the maximum collision energy at the LHC ($\sqrt{s} = 14 TeV$).

Figure 1.2: Leading order Feynman diagrams for $t\bar{t}$ production. *Up*: Via $q\bar{q}$ annihilation (dominant for the pp collision energy scale at the Tevatron). *Down*: Via gluon-gluon fusion (dominant for the collision energy scale at the LHC).

Figure 1.3: Cross sections evolution with the energy of pp collision

The $t\bar{t}$ cross section is about 100 times larger for the maximum collision energy at the LHC than for the Tevatron collision energy. The background cross section is about 10 times larger (fig. 1.3). The cross-sections for the referred processes are of the same order for pp and proton-antiproton ($p\bar{p}$) collisions at the same energy. At the Tevatron the collisions are $p\bar{p}$, while at the LHC the collisions are pp.

Figure 1.4: Branching ratios for $t\bar{t}$ decay channels

In the Standard Model of Particle Physics (SM), the top quark decays almost exclusively to a W boson and a bottom quark (99.8%) [3]. Its decay width is (in next-to-leading order) [4]:

$$\Gamma(t \rightarrow W^+b) = 1.3GeV \quad (1.1)$$

The $t\bar{t}$ decay channels are named by the two W bosons decay products. For instance, in the electron + jets channel one W decays to the electron lepton and neutrino, the other W decays to 2 quarks which will produce 2 narrow cone of hadrons and other particles produced by the hadronization of a quark or gluon with high momentums (jets) (fig. 1.4).

Several extensions of the SM may alter the rates of known physics processes. One example is the H^+ which can be detected through an anomalously large production of tau leptons in $t\bar{t}$ decays.

1.2 Charged Higgs

The Higgs Mechanism needs at least one Higgs doublet to allow particles to have mass in the Standard Model. However, there is no fundamental reason to exist just one Higgs doublet. Supersymmetry requires at least two Higgs doublets.

The Two Higgs Doublets Models (2HDM) is a class of extensions to the SM, where there are 2 Higgs Doublets instead of just one. After symmetry breaking, there are 5 Higgs bosons: the CP-even h^0 and H^0 , the pseudoscalar A^0 , and the charged higgs bosons H^+ and H^- (complex conjugates of each other, they both have the same properties except for opposite charges).

In a type II 2HDM one doublet couples only to the up quarks and the other couples only to the leptons and down quarks. A CP-conserving type II 2HDM is defined by 7 independent parameters. The Minimal Supersymmetric extension to the Standard Model (MSSM) is a type II 2HDM. Supersymmetry enforces relations amongst Higgs masses and couplings, on the one hand, and weak gauge boson masses and interaction parameters, on the other hand, in such a way that only two independent parameters survive in the MSSM: the H^+ mass and the ratio of the vacuum expectation values of the two Higgs doublets ($\tan\beta$). At tree-level, these are the only inputs needed to compute Higgs masses and couplings to ordinary matter (quarks, leptons and gauge bosons) as well as Higgs self-couplings [5]. The charged Higgs boson interactions with fermions are given by the Lagrangian:

$$\mathcal{L} = \frac{g}{\sqrt{2}m_W \tan\beta} H^+ \left\{ V_{ij} m_{u_i} \bar{u}_{iR} d_{jL} + \tan^2\beta V_{ij} m_{d_j} \bar{u}_{iL} d_{jR} + \tan^2\beta m_{\ell_j} \bar{\nu}_{jL} \ell_{jR} \right\} + H.c. \quad (1.2)$$

where V_{ij} are the Kobayashi-Maskawa (KM) matrix elements. L and R stand for left and right handed helicities [6].

Due to the mass differences, the dominant terms for the decay of the H^+ will be the ones involving the top and charm quarks and the tau lepton. A H^+ produced by the decay of the top quark has a mass smaller than the top mass and therefore the H^+ decay to a top and an antibottom quark is kinematically suppressed.

The MSSM imposes relations between the Higgs bosons masses that will kinematically suppress the decays $H^\pm \rightarrow W^\pm A^0$ and $H^\pm \rightarrow W^\pm H^0$. The $H^\pm \rightarrow W^\pm h$ decay is kinematically possible in the MSSM, but will only occur with sizable rates in a $\tan\beta$ region which is already excluded by experimental data [7, 8]. See figure 1.5 taken from [9].

From the Lagrangian, neglecting all purely kinematic factors of the bottom mass that are not enhanced by $\tan\beta$, we get the width of the top quark decay to charged Higgs and bottom quark (in Leading Order) [10]:

$$\Gamma(t \rightarrow H^+ b) = \frac{g^2 m_t^3}{16m_W^2 \pi \tan^2\beta} |V_{ij}|^2 \left\{ 1 - \left(\frac{m_{H^+}}{m_t} \right)^2 \right\} \left\{ 1 + \left(\frac{m_b \tan^2\beta}{m_t} \right)^2 \right\} \quad (1.3)$$

The Next-to-Leading order corrections to this width will be important. The Supersymmetric loop effects may change significantly this decay width, depending on extra MSSM parameters [11]. Moreover, large radiative corrections from SUSY-breaking effects can lead to a suppression of the $\text{BR}(H^+ \rightarrow \tau^+ \nu_\tau)$ compared to $\text{BR}(H^+ \rightarrow c\bar{s})$ for low $\tan\beta$. Therefore, only two simple models will be considered: a purely taonic model, where the charged Higgs decays exclusively to an antitau lepton and a neutrino, and a purely leptophobic model, where the charged Higgs boson decays exclusively to a charm and a strange quarks. The taonic model is identical to the MSSM for large values of $\tan\beta$. The leptophobic model may be similar to the MSSM for low values of $\tan\beta$ and to other Multi Higgs models [7]. On chapters 3 and 4, exclusion limits will be set on the

Figure 1.5: Branching ratios for $t \rightarrow H^\pm b$ and $H^\pm \rightarrow \tau^+ \nu_\tau$ as a function of $\tan \beta$ for a H^\pm mass of $100 \text{ GeV}/c^2$ in the MSSM and a given set of MSSM parameters.

branching ratio of the decay of the top quark to a charged Higgs boson and a bottom quark ($\text{BR}(t \rightarrow H^\pm b)$), instead of setting limits on $\tan \beta$, producing an experimental result that is independent of the Supersymmetric corrections to $\Gamma(t \rightarrow H^\pm b)$.

Figure 1.6: Most important leading order diagrams for the $t\bar{t}$ decays in the tauonic and leptophobic models.

1.3 Tau decays

The tau lepton is an elementary fermion similar to the electron, with negative electric charge. Its mass is $1777 \text{ MeV}/c^2$ (compared to $105.7 \text{ MeV}/c^2$ for muons and $0.511 \text{ MeV}/c^2$ for electrons).

The tau lifetime ($2.9 \times 10^{-13} \text{ s}$) is too small for it to reach the detector, so it is identified by his decay products. The main contributors to the tau decay are:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tau^- &\rightarrow e^- \bar{\nu}_e \nu_\tau & (18\%) \\
 \tau^- &\rightarrow \mu^- \bar{\nu}_\mu \nu_\tau & (17\%) \\
 \tau^- &\rightarrow \pi^- \nu_\tau & (11\%) \\
 \tau^- &\rightarrow \rho^- \nu_\tau \rightarrow \pi^- \pi^0 \nu_\tau & (24\%) \\
 \tau^- &\rightarrow a_1^- \nu_\tau \rightarrow \pi^- \pi^0 \pi^0 \nu_\tau & (9\%) \\
 \tau^- &\rightarrow a_1^- \nu_\tau \rightarrow \pi^+ \pi^- \pi^- \nu_\tau & (9\%)
 \end{aligned} \tag{1.4}$$

The mesons are hadrons composed of 2 valence quarks. The π , ρ and a_1 are flavourless mesons made of the isospin 1 combinations of the first generation quarks (u and d). ρ and a_1 are vector (spin=1, odd parity) mesons. The pion is the lightest meson. It is a pseudoscalar (spin=0, odd parity). The π^0 decays almost exclusively (98%). ρ , a_1 and π^0 are short lived and will decay before reach the detector. π^\pm is long lived and will be identified as a track.

A tau produced by the decay of a W, Z or H^+ bosons will have a large momentum compared to his mass and, as a consequence, his decay products will be almost collinear. The figure 1.7 shows a tau decaying into three charged particles and the second tau into one charged particle and a π^0 at the Delphi detector. The event is $e^+e^- \rightarrow Z \rightarrow \tau^+\tau^-$.

Figure 1.7: Example of a tau hadronic decay at the Delphi detector.

1.4 Tau polarization

The charged Higgs boson coupling to the tau leptons in a type II 2HDM is of the form:

$$\mathcal{L} \propto H^+ \bar{\nu}_{\tau L} \tau_R + H^- \bar{\tau}_R \nu_{\tau L} \quad (1.5)$$

Consequently, the charged Higgs decays to tau fermions are:

$$H^- \rightarrow \tau_R^- \bar{\nu}_R, H^+ \rightarrow \tau_L^+ \nu_L \quad (1.6)$$

The W boson coupling to the tau fermions in the SM is of the form:

$$\mathcal{L} \propto W_\mu^+ \bar{\nu}_{\tau L} \gamma^\mu \tau_L + W_\mu^- \bar{\tau}_L \gamma^\mu \nu_{\tau L} \quad (1.7)$$

Consequently, the W boson decays to tau fermions are:

$$W^- \rightarrow \tau_L^- \bar{\nu}_R, W^+ \rightarrow \tau_R^+ \nu_L \quad (1.8)$$

The parameter P_τ is defined as:

$$P_{\tau_R^-} = +1, \quad P_{\tau_L^-} = -1 \quad (1.9)$$

The decay width of the tau is CP invariant. It depends on P_τ (equations 1.12, 1.13, 1.14 and 1.14), so one has:

$$P_{\tau_L^\pm} = P_{\tau_R^\mp}, \quad P_{\tau_R^\pm} = P_{\tau_L^\mp} \quad (1.10)$$

The taus from H^\pm have the opposite P_τ of the taus from W^\pm :

$$P_\tau^H = +1, \quad P_\tau^W = -1. \quad (1.11)$$

The τ decays will be studied in the collinear approximation $m_\tau \ll p_\tau$, where all the decay products emerge along the τ line of flight in the laboratory frame. x is the fraction of the τ energy-momentum carried by the charged decay product (meson or lepton) in the laboratory frame.

For the τ decays into electron or muon (ℓ), the polarization of the outgoing lepton is essentially unmeasurable at high energies and so we sum over the two polarization states. Neglecting the lepton mass one has

$$\frac{1}{\Gamma_\ell} \frac{d\Gamma_\ell}{dx} = \frac{1}{3}(1-x) \left\{ (5+5x-4x^2) + P_\tau(1+x-8x^2) \right\} \quad (1.12)$$

which yields a relatively weak dependence of the lepton distribution on P_τ .

For τ hadronic decay into π or a vector meson (ρ, a_1), one has

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{\Gamma_\pi} \frac{d\Gamma_\pi}{d\cos\theta} &= \frac{1}{2}(1 + P_\tau \cos\theta) \\ \frac{1}{\Gamma_v} \frac{d\Gamma_{vL}}{d\cos\theta} &= \frac{\frac{1}{2}m_\tau^2}{m_\tau^2 + 2m_v^2}(1 + P_\tau \cos\theta) \\ \frac{1}{\Gamma_v} \frac{d\Gamma_{vT}}{d\cos\theta} &= \frac{m_v^2}{m_\tau^2 + 2m_v^2}(1 - P_\tau \cos\theta) \end{aligned} \quad (1.13)$$

where v stands for the vector meson and L, T denote its longitudinal and transverse polarization states. The angle θ measures the direction of the meson in the τ rest frame relative to the τ line of flight, which defines its polarization axis. It is related to the fraction x :

$$\cos\theta = \frac{2x - 1 - m_{\pi,v}^2/m_\tau^2}{1 - m_{\pi,v}^2/m_\tau^2}. \quad (1.14)$$

The almost collinear hadronic decay products of the tau will be identified as a jet of particles, the tau-jet. The hard (high momentum) tau-jets with $P_\tau=+1$ come mostly from the π, ρ_L and a_{1L} contributions, while the hard tau-jets with $P_\tau=-1$ come mostly from the ρ_T and a_{1T} contributions. Only the hard tau-jets will pass the p_T threshold for detecting tau-jets. It happens that the fractional energy-momentum carried by the charged pion will have a different distribution for ρ_T and a_{1T} when compared to π, ρ_L and a_{1L} . In the figure 1.8 are shown the distributions of ρ_L, ρ_T, a_{1L} and a_{1T} events in the fractional momentum carried by charged pion, X . For 3 charged pion decay the charged pion considered is the one with opposite charge of the tau. The distribution of π^\pm events is a delta function at $X=1$ [12].

Figure 1.8: Distributions of ρ_L, ρ_T, a_{1L} and a_{1T} events in the fractional momentum carried by charged pion, X .

As a consequence, the pions from taus with different polarization will have different momentum distributions:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tau_R^- &\rightarrow \pi^- \\
 &\rightarrow \pi^- \text{ hard and } \pi^0 \text{ soft} \\
 &\rightarrow \pi^0 \text{ hard and } \pi^- \text{ soft} \\
 &\rightarrow \pi^- \text{ hard and } \pi^0 \pi^0 \text{ soft} \\
 &\rightarrow \pi^0 \pi^0 \text{ hard and } \pi^- \text{ soft} \\
 &\rightarrow \pi^+ \text{ hard and } \pi^- \pi^- \text{ soft} \\
 &\rightarrow \pi^- \pi^- \text{ hard and } \pi^+ \text{ soft}
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{1.15}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tau_L^- &\rightarrow \pi^- \quad \text{and} \quad \pi^0 \text{ symmetric} \\
 &\rightarrow \pi^- \quad \text{and} \quad \pi^0 \pi^0 \text{ symmetric} \\
 &\rightarrow \pi^+ \quad \text{and} \quad \pi^- \pi^- \text{ symmetric}
 \end{aligned}$$

1.5 Current limits

Measurements at LEP [13] in the 2HDM scenario have excluded the existence of the charged Higgs with masses lower than $\sim 80 \text{ GeV}/c^2$. The current limits on the branching ratio $\text{BR}(t \rightarrow H^\pm b)$ are established from the CDF [14] [15] and D0 [7] experiments at the Tevatron for the tauonic and leptophobic models. The unexplored territory includes a H^\pm mass region between ~ 80 and $\sim 160 \text{ GeV}/c^2$, and values of $\text{BR}(t \rightarrow H^\pm b)$ smaller than around 15% in both tauonic and leptophobic models.

Figure 1.9: Current exclusion limits from the D0 experiment at Tevatron. Left: Tauonic Model. Right: Leptophobic model.

Chapter 2

The CMS experiment

Most of the contents of this chapter were taken from [16].

2.1 LHC

The first goal of the Large Hadron Collider (LHC) experiment is to search for the SM Higgs boson. After one year of operation at just below design luminosity (which will give $10fb^{-1}$ of data) the Standard Model Higgs boson should be either discovered at the LHC experiments, or excluded. There are alternative models to describe our world, for example supersymmetry, which may be testable at the TeV energy scale.

Hadron colliders are well suited to the task of exploring new energy domains, and the region of 1 TeV constituent center-of-mass energy can be explored if the proton energy and the luminosity are high enough. The collisions will take place between quarks and gluons, within the proton, hence carrying just a fraction of the full proton energy.

The 27km circumference Large Hadron Collider has been constructed in a tunnel 100m underground. It delivers proton beams with energy 7 TeV and at a design luminosity of $L = 1034cm^{-2}s^{-1}$. These parameters provide a seven-fold increase in energy and a hundred-fold increase in integrated luminosity over the other hadron collider experiments at the Tevatron.

2.2 CMS detector

The Compact Muon Solenoid (CMS) experiment is one of four detectors built at crossing sites of the LHC beams, and is one of two general purpose detectors.

With a beam spacing of 25 ns, beam crossings occur in the CMS detector at a rate of 40MHz. Approximately 25 interactions occur with each beam crossing, thus giving 1 billion events occurring in the CMS detector every second. In order to extract physics from these interactions it is vital to have fast electronics, very good resolution and very precise triggering.

The symmetrical CMS detector is built in a traditional barrel design with two endcaps to provide a larger coverage (Absolute value of the pseudo-rapidity ($|\eta| < 5$)). The CMS detector is a compact design, and is specifically built to provide good muon detection and resolution. Particle identification is aided by the superconducting solenoid which provides a 4 Tesla magnetic field.

2.3 Inner Tracker

The inner tracker sits around the LHC beam-pipe. It is cylindrical in shape, of length 5.8 m, and has a diameter of 2.6 m, and consists of 25,000 silicon strip sensors. The system will provide analogue data from 10 million channels of the micro-strip tracker. The CMS tracking system is designed to reconstruct high p_T

Figure 2.1: A candidate for production of a top quark pair in CMS where both top quarks decay into a W and a b quark, and both W particles decay into a muon and neutrino. This results in 2 muons (red tracks), 2 jets tagged as b-quark jets and missing energy (from the escaping neutrinos).

Figure 2.2: CMS Detector Components

muons, isolated electrons and hadrons with high momentum resolution and an efficiency better than 98% in the range $|\eta| < 2.5$.

The inner-most tracking material consists of 3 layers of silicon pixel detectors which are placed close to the interaction region to improve the measurement of the impact parameter of charged-particle tracks, as well as the position of secondary vertices. In order to deal with high track multiplicities, CMS employs 10 layers of silicon microstrip detectors, which provide the required granularity and precision.

Accurate measurement of secondary vertices is required to study b quark decays, for instance.

2.4 Calorimetry

Electrons, photons and hadrons will be stopped by the calorimeters allowing their energy to be measured. The first calorimeter layer is designed to measure the energies of electrons and photons with high precision. Strongly-interacting particles, hadrons, deposit most of their energy in the second layer, the hadron calorimeter. Muons and tau leptons deposit only a very small fraction of their energy in the calorimeters, and are detected by consulting also with tracking and muon detector subsystems. Neutrinos escape detection, but their presence can be inferred from an apparent energy imbalance in the interaction.

Electromagnetic Calorimeter (ECAL)

CMS has a very compact scintillating crystal calorimeter which offers excellent performance for energy resolution since almost all of the energy of electrons and photons is deposited within the crystal volume. The Electromagnetic calorimeter (ECAL) uses over 80,000 lead-tungstate (PbWO₄) crystals with coverage in pseudorapidity up to $|\eta| < 3.0$. The crystals convert energy into light, and the scintillation light is detected by silicon avalanche photodiodes (APDs) in the barrel region ($|\eta| < 1.5$) and vacuum phototriodes (VPTs) in the endcap region ($1.5 < |\eta| < 3$).

A preshower system is installed in front of the endcap ECAL for pi-zero rejection and the detection of photons. This is designed to detect the slightly-overlapping pair of photons from a π^0 decay and to distinguish these from the single shower produced from a single photon interacting with the calorimeter material .

Hadronic Calorimeter (HCAL)

The ECAL is surrounded by a brass/scintillator sampling Hadron Calorimeter (HCAL) with coverage up to $|\eta| < 3.0$. The HCAL plays an essential role in the identification and measurement of quarks, gluons, and neutrinos by measuring the energy and direction of jets and of missing transverse energy in events.

The scintillation light is converted by wavelength-shifting fibers embedded in the scintillator tiles and channeled to photodetectors via clear fibers. This light is detected by hybrid photodiodes that can provide gain and operate in high axial magnetic fields. While most of the hadron calorimetry is contained inside the CMS magnet, there are several additional layers outside the magnet to detect particles from high energy showers.

The central calorimetry is complemented by a "tail-catcher" in the barrel region - ensuring that hadronic showers are sampled with nearly 11 hadronic interaction lengths. This "depth" of the HCAL is needed to contain high-energy jets and also to filter out hadrons from jets involving also muons.

The hadron calorimeter has both barrel and endcap components which are sampling calorimeters with 50 mm thick copper absorber plates interleaved with 4 mm thick scintillator sheets. There are also "forward" hadron calorimeters installed at each end of the CMS detector which provide coverage up to $|\eta| < 5.0$. Here steel absorber plates are used in the harsher radiation environment of the forward systems and hadronic showers are seen by radiation-resistant quartz-fibres. The Cerenkov light emitted in the quartz fibres is detected by conventional photomultiplier tubes. The forward calorimeters ensure full geometric coverage for the measurement of the missing transverse energy in the event.

2.5 Superconducting Magnet

At the heart of CMS sits a 13-m-long, 5.9 m inner diameter, 12,000 ton, 4 T superconducting solenoid which in part gives CMS its name. The CMS magnet system consists of a superconducting coil, the magnet yoke,

a vacuum tank and ancillaries such as cryogenics, power supplies and process controls. Inside the bore of the magnet sit the inner tracker and the calorimetry, while outside is the flux return system and muon detection.

In order to achieve good momentum resolution with a compact spectrometer it is necessary to have a combination of a high magnetic field and high precision on the spatial resolution and alignment of the detectors. The momentum measurement of charged particles in the detector is based on the bending of their trajectories.

2.6 Muon Chambers

Muons are expected to provide clean signatures for a wide range of physics processes.

The return field of the solenoid is large enough to saturate 1.5 m of iron, allowing 4 muon "stations" to be interleaved with the iron return yoke plates of the magnet system. This provides a muon system with reconstruction efficiency better than 98% over the full pseudorapidity range.

Each muon station consists of several layers of aluminium drift tubes (DT) in the barrel region and cathode strip chambers (CSCs) in the endcap region, complemented by resistive plate chambers (RPCs). The muon detectors are arranged in concentric cylinders around the beam line in the barrel region, and in disks perpendicular to the beam line in the endcaps. Muon identification is ensured by the large thickness of the absorber material (iron), which cannot be traversed by particles other than neutrinos and muons. The DT and CSC detectors are used to obtain a precise measurement of the position and thus the momentum of the muons, whereas the RPC chambers are dedicated to providing fast information for the Level-1 trigger.

2.7 Particle Detection

Figure 2.3: Particle detection

The figure 2.3 shows a summary of the particle detection process in CMS. Charged particles leave signatures in the inner tracking system, and the vertices from decaying short-lived particles like b quarks can be identified. Photons, electrons, neutral pions and kaons are stopped in the crystals of the electromagnetic calorimeter and the scintillation light is used to determine the deposited energy. Hadrons punch through further and are generally stopped by the hadronic calorimeter where jets are confined and only the highest-energy hadrons and muons pass through the superconducting solenoid into the outer regions of the CMS barrel. Finally, muons are detected in the various muon detectors which interleave the return yoke of the magnet.

Neutrinos escape from the CMS detector and are inferred from an imbalance of energy in the reconstructed event.

Due to the powerful magnetic field, the trajectories of charged particles are bent in a direction perpendicular to the magnetic field. The direction of bending depends on the charge of the particle, while the amount of bending is a function of particle momentum - this is a central feature of particle identification in modern particle physics detectors. After particles pass through the solenoid, their bending is in the opposite direction, as indicated by figure 2.3. This is due to the fact that the magnetic field is in the opposite direction.

2.8 Trigger and Data Acquisition

The Trigger and Data Acquisition System is designed to select the most interesting events for storage and further analysis.

The first level of triggering, Level 1 (L1), is a hardware trigger, using hardware processors to rapidly select or reject events based on information from the ECAL and muon RPCs. Calorimeter triggering is based on a first measurement of energy deposition in the crystals, whereas the muon triggering centres around transverse momentum measurements of muons. The Level 1 trigger reduces the event rate from 40MHz to 100kHz.

An event passing the L1 trigger decision is transmitted to the Data Acquisition System where information from the 16M channels in the CMS subdetector systems is combined by the event builder into a single event. This event is then challenged by the next level of triggering.

The High Level Trigger (HLT) is a software-based trigger which performs a more sophisticated analysis of the event, including applying fast pattern recognition algorithms and event reconstruction. The main reduction factor for events passing the Level 1 triggering is obtained by using tracker information. The HLT decision reduces the event rate to about 100Hz for storage and later offline analysis.

2.9 Computing and Grid resources

CMS presents challenges also in terms of the data volume and the necessary computing resources. Data sets and resource requirements are at least one order of magnitude larger than in previous experiments.

The CMS computing environment has been constructed as a distributed system of computing services and resources that interact with each other as Grid services. The computational infrastructure is intended to be available to CMS collaborators, independently of their physical locations, and on a fair share basis.

The computing centers available to CMS around the world are distributed and configured in a tiered architecture that functions as a single coherent system. Each of the three tier levels (T0, T1, T2) provides different resources and services.

There are about 36 T2 sites (one at Laboratory of Instrumentation and Experimental Particle Physics (LIP)), each associated with one of the seven T1 sites or directly to the T0 at CERN (figures 2.4 and 2.5):

CMS Data is arranged into an hierarchy of data tiers. Each physics event is written into each data tier, where the tiers each contain different levels of information about the event. The two main data tiers written in CMS are:

1. RAW: full event information from the Tier-0 (i.e. from CERN), containing 'raw' detector information (detector element hits, etc).

2. RECO ("RECO"nstructed data"): the output from first-pass processing by the Tier-0. This layer contains the reconstructed physics objects.

Data is stored as ROOT files. The smallest unit in computing space is the file block which corresponds to a group of ROOT files likely to be accessed together. CMS has a global data catalog called the Dataset Bookkeeping System (DBS) which provides mapping between the dataset and the list of corresponding fileblocks.

There are three principle areas of workflow in CMS:

1. At Tier2 Centres: Monte Carlo events are generated, detector interactions simulated, events reconstructed in the same manner as will be applied to data, and the events are then moved to tape storage for later use

2. At The Tier0 Center: Data is received from the CMS detector experiment, the reconstruction algorithms are run and RAW and RECO are exported to Tier1 sites

3. The user prepare analysis code, send code to site where there is appropriate data, then the code runs on the data and the results are collected. The process of finding the sites with data and CPU, running the jobs, and collecting the results is all managed by the CRAB software.

Figure 2.4: Tier structure

Figure 2.5: CMS computing centers around the world. Tiers 1 in red and Tiers 2 in blue.

Chapter 3

Preliminary study at 10 TeV

3.1 Analysis approach

This study focuses on the mass range $100 \leq M_{H^\pm} \leq 160 \text{ GeV}/c^2$, with $\text{BR}(H^+ \rightarrow \tau^+ \nu_\tau) = 1$. If the H^\pm exists we may observe an excess of events in the $\tau\ell$ channel in the LHC early data incompatible with the Standard Model ($\ell = e, \mu$).

3.2 Data samples

The analysis is performed on two different type of data samples: the "official" Monte Carlo (MC) samples, and privately generated $t\bar{t}$ samples (with decays to charged Higgs boson). In order to check the quality of the privately generated samples, a control sample containing only SM $t\bar{t}$ events is also generated and studied.

SM background samples

The main backgrounds in the $t\bar{t} \tau\ell$ channel are $W/Z + jets$ events. Samples used are produced with Madgraph [17] of the "official" Fall08 MC production (see Tab. 3.1), where different jet multiplicities ($t\bar{t}/W/Z + n$ jets, $n = 0, 1, 2, 3, 4$) are available. The cross sections are taken from the production page [18].

Table 3.1: Samples used for the background estimation and cross-check with the SM scenario.

Name	Dataset	Events	Xsection	Int. luminosity
$t\bar{t} + \text{Jets}$	/TTJets-madgraph/Fall08_IDEAL_V11_redigi_v10/GEN-SIM-RECO	$\sim 1 \text{ M}$	414 pb NLO	2.3 fb^{-1}
$W + \text{Jets}$	/WJets-madgraph/Fall08_IDEAL_V11_redigi_v1/GEN-SIM-RECO	$\sim 10 \text{ M}$	$35.6 \mu\text{b}$ NLO	0.26 fb^{-1}
$Z + \text{Jets}$	/ZJets-madgraph/Fall08_IDEAL_V11_redigi_v1/GEN-SIM-RECO	$\sim 1 \text{ M}$	$3.5 \mu\text{b}$ NLO	0.33 fb^{-1}
Single Top	/SingleTop_sChannel/Summer08_IDEAL_V11_redigi_v3/GEN-SIM-RECO	$\sim 12 \text{ k}$	5 pb NLO	2.4 fb^{-1}
	/SingleTop_tChannel/Summer08_IDEAL_V11_redigi_v3/GEN-SIM-RECO	$\sim 290 \text{ k}$	130 pb NLO	2.2 fb^{-1}
	/SingleTop_tWChannel/Summer08_IDEAL_V11_redigi_v3/GEN-SIM-RECO	$\sim 170 \text{ k}$	29 pb NLO	6.0 fb^{-1}
QCD	/QCD100to250-madgraph/Fall08_IDEAL_V9_v4/GEN-SIM-RECO	$\sim 14 \text{ M}$	$15 \times 10^6 \text{ pb}$ LO	0.95 pb^{-1}
	/QCD250to500-madgraph/Fall08_IDEAL_V9_v1/GEN-SIM-RECO	$\sim 5 \text{ M}$	$400 \times 10^3 \text{ pb}$ LO	13.4 pb^{-1}
	/QCD500to1000-madgraph/Fall08_IDEAL_V9_v1/GEN-SIM-RECO	$\sim 5 \text{ M}$	$14 \times 10^3 \text{ pb}$ LO	351.6 pb^{-1}
	/QCD1000toInf-madgraph/Fall08_IDEAL_V9_v1/GEN-SIM-RECO	$\sim 1 \text{ M}$	370 pb LO	2827.2 pb^{-1}

Signal samples

Madgraph [17] is used for the generation of the signal samples. TAUOLA [19] is used for correctly simulating the tau decay/polarization in the privately generated samples for the signal and Fastsim is used to simulate the interaction of the generated particles with the detector [20]. In order to cross check the consistency of the results obtained using the "official" MadGraph samples, three different configurations are used:

1. MadGraph *without* TAUOLA;
2. MadGraph *with* TAUOLA;
3. MadGraph *with* TAUOLA, where the value $\text{BR}(t \rightarrow Wb) = 1$ is forced.

Samples in 1) and 2) are used to check the consistency (see Sec. 3.4) between the "official" and the privately generated samples, while samples in 3) are used in the analysis to determine the event yield and set the limits. The generated datasets are available in the *DBS* database [21]. For each H^\pm mass (100, 120, 140, and 160 GeV/c^2), events are generated for the processes: a) $t\bar{t} \rightarrow H^+W^-b\bar{b}$, b) $t\bar{t} \rightarrow W^+H^-b\bar{b}$, and c) $t\bar{t} \rightarrow H^+H^-b\bar{b}$. Throughout this manuscript, these samples will be referred to as "WH" (a and b) and "HH" (c), respectively.

Table 3.2: List of generated H^\pm samples using MadGraph and Tauola for $\sqrt{s} = 10 \text{ TeV}$.

Description	Dataset	Events
$M(H^+) = 100 \text{ GeV}/c^2$	/Mad_XQ30_10TeV_TAUOLA_FASTSIM_IDEALV11_HW100	220000
$M(H^+) = 120 \text{ GeV}/c^2$	/Mad_XQ30_10TeV_TAUOLA_FASTSIM_IDEALV11_HW120	210000
$M(H^+) = 140 \text{ GeV}/c^2$	/Mad_XQ30_10TeV_TAUOLA_FASTSIM_IDEALV11_HW140	230000
$M(H^+) = 160 \text{ GeV}/c^2$	/Mad_XQ30_10TeV_TAUOLA_FASTSIM_IDEALV11_HW160	245000
$M(H^-) = 100 \text{ GeV}/c^2$	/Mad_XQ30_10TeV_TAUOLA_FASTSIM_IDEALV11_WH100	255000
$M(H^-) = 120 \text{ GeV}/c^2$	/Mad_XQ30_10TeV_TAUOLA_FASTSIM_IDEALV11_WH120	260000
$M(H^-) = 140 \text{ GeV}/c^2$	/Mad_XQ30_10TeV_TAUOLA_FASTSIM_IDEALV11_WH140	215000
$M(H^-) = 160 \text{ GeV}/c^2$	/Mad_XQ30_10TeV_TAUOLA_FASTSIM_IDEALV11_WH160	205000
$M(H^\pm) = 100 \text{ GeV}/c^2$	/Mad_XQ30_10TeV_TAUOLA_FASTSIM_IDEALV11_HH100	300000
$M(H^\pm) = 120 \text{ GeV}/c^2$	/Mad_XQ30_10TeV_TAUOLA_FASTSIM_IDEALV11_HH120	260000
$M(H^\pm) = 140 \text{ GeV}/c^2$	/Mad_XQ30_10TeV_TAUOLA_FASTSIM_IDEALV11_HH140	220000
$M(H^\pm) = 160 \text{ GeV}/c^2$	/Mad_XQ30_10TeV_TAUOLA_FASTSIM_IDEALV11_HH160	260000
SM: $t\bar{t} \rightarrow W^+W^-b\bar{b}$	/Mad_XQ30_10TeV_TAUOLA_FASTSIM_IDEALV11_WW	255000

3.3 Reconstruction tools and trigger

The tools used for the reconstruction of the physics objects (i.e. leptons, jets and missing transverse energy) are provided by the framework and software tools defined by the respective CMS Physics Objects Groups (POGs). The Physics Analysis Tools (PAT) layer for the CMSSW framework is used in this analysis. The software version used is CMSSW 2.2.13.

3.4 Event selection

The final state consists of one lepton (electron or muon), one hadronic tau decay, at least two jets from the hadronization of the b quarks, and missing transverse energy (\cancel{E}_T), due to the production of two neutrinos. The event selection is similar to the one described in [22], which is summarized in the following. The only difference is in the b -tagging selection, which is not used to set the BR limits.

Trigger selection: The logical *or* of the inclusive electron, HLT_Ele15_LW_L1R, or inclusive muon triggers, HLT_Mu9, is used. More details concerning the use of L1+HLT single lepton triggers are available in [23].

Lepton selection: At least one isolated electron or muon with $p_T > 20 \text{ GeV}/c$ and $|\eta| \leq 2.4$ is required. Prompt lepton decays are selected by requiring the impact parameter to be smaller than $400 \mu\text{m}$.

Electron candidates are defined using the cut-based electron ID tag [24] chosen from the `allLayer1Electrons` collection. Muon candidates are defined from the `allLayer1Muons` collection. The lepton categories required are `eidTight` for electrons and `GlobalMuon` for muons.

In order to distinguish prompt leptons originated from W decays from those coming from other sources, such as jets or due to mis-reconstruction, lepton isolation is required for both electrons and muons. Tracking and calorimeter isolation are defined as:

$$\text{iso}_{track} : \frac{p_{\text{T}}^{\text{lepton}}}{p_{\text{T}}^{\text{lepton}} + \sum p_{\text{T}}^{\text{track}}} > 0.9, \quad \text{iso}_{calo} : \begin{cases} \frac{p_{\text{T}}^e}{p_{\text{T}}^e + \sum E_{\text{T}}^{\text{calo}}} > 0.8 \\ \frac{p_{\text{T}}^\mu}{p_{\text{T}}^\mu + \sum E_{\text{T}}^{\text{calo}}} > 0.9 \end{cases} \quad (3.1)$$

Jet selection: At least two jets with $p_{\text{T}} > 30$ GeV/c and $|\eta| < 2.4$ are required. The standard jet energy corrections (L2+L3, more details available in [25]) are applied and the SC5 jet reconstruction algorithm is used. Additional quality cuts are required, namely each jet is required to have a minimum of two calorimeter towers ($N_{tower} \geq 2$) and at least one associated track ($N_{track} \geq 1$). Jets with large electromagnetic fraction ($\text{EmF} > 0.98$) are removed.

Missing transverse energy (\cancel{E}_{T}): A cut is applied ($\cancel{E}_{\text{T}} > 40$ GeV). \cancel{E}_{T} is corrected for jet energy corrections and for muons.

Tau selection: Tau lepton identification is documented in more detail in [26] and in [22] ("improved" tau-ID). At least one hadronically decaying τ with one or three charged tracks (prongs) is required. The leading track (with the highest p_{T}) is chosen with $p_{\text{T}} > 20$ GeV/c and $|\eta| < 2.4$, and with a "signal" cone of $R = 0.07$ and an "isolation" cone of $R = 0.5$.

Tau leptons may be contaminated by the presence of electrons and muons. In order to reduce the contamination, two variables are used in the event selection: electromagnetic fraction (EMF) for electron veto,

$$\text{EMF} : \frac{E_{\text{ECAL}}^{\text{jet}}}{E_{\text{ECAL}}^{\text{jet}} + E_{\text{HCAL}}^{\text{jet}}}, \quad (3.2)$$

and E/P for muon veto,

$$E/P = \frac{E^{\text{jet}}}{p^{\text{leadTrk}}} \quad (3.3)$$

Electrons are vetoed by requiring a cut on $\text{EMF} < 0.9$, since electrons are supposed to deposit most of their energy in the Electromagnetic Calorimeter (ECAL). Muons deposit little energy in the calorimeters and a cut on $E/p > 0.5$ is applied to all tau-tagged candidates.

A cut on the p_{T} of tracks within the isolation cone (i.e. $0.07 < \Delta R < 0.5$) is applied ($\sum^{\text{iso}} p_{\text{T}}^{\text{iso}} = 0$), to guarantee that no other charged tracks are in the isolation cone. ECAL isolation is also required: $\sum^{\text{ECAL}} E_{\text{T}} < 3(3.5)$ GeV for 1 (3) prong(s).

The pseudo-rapidity regions $1.46 < |\eta| < 1.56$, where ECAL Barrel and Endcap calorimeter meet are excluded. Electrons pointing at the ECAL crack region leave their energy in the HCAL calorimeter, and therefore have small electromagnetic energy fraction.

Opposite sign: The charge sum of the lepton and tau must be zero.

b -tagging: This cut is not used here, but it is studied for future higher luminosity scenarios. At least two jets identified as b -jets (b -tagged). A combined secondary vertex-based b -tagging algorithm is used [27] for the identification of b -jets ($p_{\text{T}} > 30$ GeV/c, $|\eta| < 2.4$). The b -tagging discriminator is defined by combining topological and kinematical variables with the track impact parameter significances. The average b -tagging discriminator is required to be larger than 0.4 (more details in Sec. 3.5).

All cuts are applied sequentially. Up to the level of the \cancel{E}_{T} cut (before applying the τ isolation cuts) we use the global denomination "W+jets" for the events that have passed this selection.

Event yield for the SM background and consistency checks

The validity of the samples privately generated are tested for consistency against the "officially" produced samples at different steps of the selection cuts. The samples used for the consistency test and their characteristics are:

MadOfficialFullSim: Official Summer08 samples produced using MadGraph with Full Simulation (Full-Sim) [28];

MadOfficialFastSim: Official Summer08 samples produced using MadGraph with Fast Simulation (Fast-Sim) [20];

Mad: Private MadGraph samples generated with FastSim;

MadTAUOLA: Private MadGraph samples generated with FastSim. TAUOLA is used for the proper simulation of tau decays;

MadTAUOLA_{BR=1}: Private MadGraph+TAUOLA samples generated with FastSim. The branching ratio $BR(t \rightarrow Wb)$ is forced to 1.

Comparison of the event yields obtained with these samples are shown in Tab. 3.3 for the "W+jets" selection, and in Tab. 3.4 and Tab. 3.5 for the 1- and 3-prong selections, respectively. The event yields are compatible within statistical uncertainties with the results in [22].

Table 3.3: Event yield comparison between different samples after the "W + jets" cut. Only SM $t\bar{t}$ events are used.

Sample	Init	Trigger	$N_{lep} \geq 1$	$N_{jets} \geq 2$	$\cancel{E}_T > 40$ GeV
MadOfficialFullsim	82800.0 \pm 89.5	58997.4 \pm 75.5	23361.6 \pm 47.6	20710.5 \pm 44.8	15005.2 \pm 38.1
MadOfficialFastsim	82800.0 \pm 58.6	50111.7 \pm 45.6	22890.3 \pm 30.8	20509.4 \pm 29.2	14732.4 \pm 24.7
Mad	82800.0 \pm 129.3	50880.8 \pm 101.4	22791.4 \pm 67.8	20232.2 \pm 64.0	14855.1 \pm 54.7
MadTAUOLA	82800.0 \pm 149.9	50574.7 \pm 117.2	22784.2 \pm 78.6	20163.9 \pm 74.0	14774.8 \pm 63.3
MadTAUOLA _{BR=1}	82800.0 \pm 164.0	50720.4 \pm 128.3	22875.5 \pm 86.2	20218.8 \pm 81.1	14809.2 \pm 69.3

Table 3.4: Event yield comparison between different samples by selecting 1-prong hadronic τ leptons (SM $t\bar{t}$ events).

Sample (1-prong)	"W+jets"	$N_{taus} \geq 1$	OS
MadOfficialFullsim	15005.2 \pm 38.1	187.0 \pm 4.3	166.0 \pm 4.0
MadOfficialFastsim	14732.4 \pm 24.7	178.9 \pm 2.7	153.6 \pm 2.5
Mad	14855.1 \pm 54.7	194.2 \pm 6.3	165.0 \pm 5.8
MadTAUOLA	14774.8 \pm 63.3	170.9 \pm 6.9	141.1 \pm 6.2
MadTAUOLA _{BR=1}	14809.2 \pm 69.3	171.0 \pm 7.5	149.0 \pm 7.0

Table 3.5: Event yield comparison between different samples by selecting 3-prong hadronic τ leptons (SM $t\bar{t}$ events).

Sample (3-prongs)	"W+jets"	$N_{taus} \geq 1$	OS
MadOfficialFullsim	15005.2 \pm 38.1	104.1 \pm 3.2	81.1 \pm 2.8
MadOfficialFastsim	14732.4 \pm 24.7	103.1 \pm 2.1	74.7 \pm 1.8
Mad	14855.1 \pm 54.7	112.8 \pm 4.8	80.2 \pm 4.0
MadTAUOLA	14774.8 \pm 63.3	107.1 \pm 5.4	77.4 \pm 4.6
MadTAUOLA _{BR=1}	14809.2 \pm 69.3	104.2 \pm 5.8	77.0 \pm 5.1

Figure 3.1 shows the comparison between the p_T spectra of b -jets (left) and the leading track transverse momentum of the reconstructed tau leptons (right) in the different SM $t\bar{t}$ samples. Distributions show good agreement for all samples.

Figure 3.1: *Left*: Transverse momentum of the leading b -jet. *Right*: Transverse momentum of the leading track associated to the tau lepton. Distributions are shown after the " $N_{jet} \geq 2$ " cut, and are compared for different SM $t\bar{t}$ samples. Objects are matched to MC.

Tables 3.6, 3.7 and 3.8 list the event yields discriminated for each channel, for the MadTAUOLA $_{BR=1}$ $t\bar{t}$ sample. Only SM events are listed. The event yields for "other $t\bar{t}$ ", W/Z+jets, single Top and QCD events are obtained using the "official" samples (Sec. 3.2).

Table 3.6: Event yields detailed for each channel, up to the “ $W + jets$ ”-like selection, for the SM $t\bar{t}$ sample generated with MadTAUOLA $_{BR=1}$. Event yields for the "other bkg" decay channels are obtained using the "official" production samples.

SM decay		Init	Trigger	$N_{lep} \geq 1$	$N_{jets} \geq 2$	$\cancel{E}_T > 40$ GeV
"τ-dil"	$e\tau$	1481.0 ± 21.9	1189.1 ± 19.6	862.1 ± 16.7	688.1 ± 14.9	547.5 ± 13.3
	$\mu\tau$	1451.1 ± 21.7	1191.3 ± 19.7	874.4 ± 16.9	700.1 ± 15.1	551.7 ± 13.4
other $t\bar{t}$	$\ell(\bar{q}_1 q_2)$	28531.9 ± 96.3	23356.1 ± 87.1	16512.6 ± 73.2	15629.1 ± 71.2	11178.3 ± 60.2
	$\ell\ell$	5424.2 ± 42.0	5098.9 ± 40.7	4518.3 ± 38.3	3237.6 ± 32.4	2578.8 ± 28.9
	$\tau(\bar{q}_1 q_2)$	7722.5 ± 50.1	3214.6 ± 32.3	29.5 ± 3.1	27.0 ± 3.0	20.1 ± 2.6
	$\tau\tau$	404.6 ± 11.5	148.1 ± 6.9	1.3 ± 0.6	1.0 ± 0.6	0.6 ± 0.5
	full-had.	37784.7 ± 110.8	16522.3 ± 73.2	77.3 ± 5.0	75.7 ± 5.0	35.7 ± 3.4
other bkg	$Z + j$	$(7000.0 \pm 6.2) \times 10^2$	$(4057.7 \pm 4.7) \times 10^2$	$(3173.9 \pm 4.2) \times 10^2$	11705.5 ± 80.6	2507.7 ± 37.3
	$W + j$	$(7120.0 \pm 2.3) \times 10^3$	$(2827.1 \pm 1.4) \times 10^3$	$(2079.0 \pm 1.2) \times 10^3$	53568.3 ± 200.8	28742.3 ± 147.1
	QCD	$(30828.7 \pm 8.0) \times 10^5$	$(4340.0 \pm 3.0) \times 10^5$	$(106.6 \pm 1.4) \times 10^4$	240476.5 ± 6417.4	43277.5 ± 2524.4
	S. Top	32800.0 ± 51.1	21576.8 ± 41.5	11481.6 ± 30.6	5526.9 ± 20.7	3603.9 ± 16.7
	S/B	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00	0.01 ± 0.00
	S/\sqrt{B}	0.05 ± 0.38	0.11 ± 0.80	0.93 ± 3.63	2.42 ± 13.50	3.62 ± 15.12

Table 3.7: Event yield for 1-prong hadronic tau decays, for the SM $t\bar{t}$ samples generated with MadTAUOLA $_{BR=1}$.

SM 1-prong		"W+jets"	$N_{taus(1-prong)} \geq 1$	OS	b-tag
"τ dilepton"	$e\tau$	547.5 ± 13.3	41.2 ± 3.7	40.9 ± 3.6	31.2 ± 3.2
	$\mu\tau$	551.7 ± 13.4	45.1 ± 3.8	44.5 ± 3.8	35.1 ± 3.4
other $t\bar{t}$	$\ell(\bar{q}_1 q_2)$	11178.3 ± 60.2	76.3 ± 5.0	58.4 ± 4.4	37.7 ± 3.5
	$\ell\ell$	2578.8 ± 28.9	7.8 ± 1.6	5.2 ± 1.3	3.9 ± 1.1
	$\tau(\bar{q}_1 q_2)$	20.1 ± 2.6	0.3 ± 0.3	0.0 ± 0.0	0.0 ± 0.0
	$\tau\tau$	0.6 ± 0.5	0.0 ± 0.0	0.0 ± 0.0	0.0 ± 0.0
	full-had.	35.7 ± 3.4	0.3 ± 0.3	0.0 ± 0.0	0.0 ± 0.0
other bkg	$Z + j$	2507.7 ± 37.3	35.5 ± 4.4	31.6 ± 4.2	3.9 ± 1.5
	$W + j$	28742.3 ± 147.1	33.1 ± 5.0	24.8 ± 4.3	2.3 ± 1.3
	QCD	43277.5 ± 2524.4	4.3 ± 1.5	1.3 ± 0.8	0.0 ± 0.0
	Single Top	3603.9 ± 16.7	11.8 ± 0.8	9.4 ± 0.7	6.3 ± 0.6
	S/B	0.01 ± 0.00	0.51 ± 0.04	0.65 ± 0.06	1.23 ± 0.13
	S/\sqrt{B}	3.62 ± 15.12	6.64 ± 2.25	7.47 ± 2.53	9.01 ± 2.66

Table 3.8: Event yield for 3-prong tau decays, for the SM $t\bar{t}$ samples generated with MadTAUOLA $_{BR=1}$.

SM 3-prong		"W+jets"	$N_{taus(3-prongs)} \geq 1$	OS	b-tag
"τ dilepton"	$e\tau$	547.5 ± 13.3	15.3 ± 2.2	13.3 ± 2.1	8.1 ± 1.6
	$\mu\tau$	551.7 ± 13.4	14.9 ± 2.2	14.6 ± 2.2	10.1 ± 1.8
other $t\bar{t}$	$\ell(\bar{q}_1 q_2)$	11178.3 ± 60.2	69.8 ± 4.8	45.8 ± 3.9	27.9 ± 3.0
	$\ell\ell$	2578.8 ± 28.9	3.9 ± 1.1	1.0 ± 0.6	0.6 ± 0.5
	$\tau(\bar{q}_1 q_2)$	20.1 ± 2.6	0.0 ± 0.0	0.0 ± 0.0	0.0 ± 0.0
	$\tau\tau$	0.6 ± 0.5	0.0 ± 0.0	0.0 ± 0.0	0.0 ± 0.0
	full-had.	35.7 ± 3.4	0.3 ± 0.3	0.0 ± 0.0	0.0 ± 0.0
other bkg	$Z + j$	2507.7 ± 37.3	5.5 ± 1.8	3.9 ± 1.5	0.6 ± 0.6
	$W + j$	28742.3 ± 147.1	36.1 ± 5.2	27.1 ± 4.5	2.3 ± 1.3
	QCD	43277.5 ± 2524.4	62.8 ± 30.0	61.1 ± 29.9	59.9 ± 29.9
	Single Top	3603.9 ± 16.7	9.8 ± 0.8	6.9 ± 0.7	4.3 ± 0.5
	S/B	0.01 ± 0.00	0.16 ± 0.03	0.19 ± 0.05	0.19 ± 0.07
	S/\sqrt{B}	3.62 ± 15.12	2.20 ± 2.48	2.31 ± 2.94	1.86 ± 2.88

Event yield for the MSSM charged Higgs

In order to estimate the number of events due to the charged Higgs contribution in the $t\bar{t}$ tau dilepton final state, samples are generated for different Higgs masses: 100, 120, 140 and 160 GeV/c². For each mass, three different processes are generated: $t\bar{t} \rightarrow W^+ H^- b\bar{b}$, $t\bar{t} \rightarrow W^- H^+ b\bar{b}$ and $t\bar{t} \rightarrow H^+ H^- b\bar{b}$. The event yields are estimated by applying the event selection described above. Results in all tables are normalized to an integrated luminosity of L=200 pb⁻¹ (the $t\bar{t}$ cross section value used is $\sigma=414$ pb⁻¹ at $\sqrt{s}=10$ TeV).

Tables 3.9, 3.10 and 3.11 show the event yields (assuming a charged Higgs boson with a mass of 120 GeV/c²) for the process $t\bar{t} \rightarrow W^\pm H^\mp b\bar{b}$. The event yield in the $e\tau$ and $\mu\tau$ channels due to the charged Higgs decays is significantly higher with respect to the SM (see Tabs. 3.6, 3.7 and 3.8).

Table 3.9: Event yields for MSSM $t\bar{t} \rightarrow H^\pm W^\mp b\bar{b}$ ($M_{H^\pm}=120$ GeV/c²).

MSSM		Init	Trigger	$N_{lep} \geq 1$	$N_{jets} \geq 2$	$\cancel{E}_T > 40$ GeV
$M_H = 120$ GeV/c ²	$e\tau$	7819.2 ± 49.9	5986.8 ± 43.7	4196.7 ± 36.6	3130.5 ± 31.6	2509.5 ± 28.3
	$\mu\tau$	7777.5 ± 49.8	6300.8 ± 44.8	4377.6 ± 37.3	3345.8 ± 32.6	2702.8 ± 29.3
	$\ell(\bar{q}_1 q_2)$	20014.4 ± 79.8	12119.7 ± 62.1	5011.9 ± 40.0	4647.0 ± 38.5	3711.7 ± 34.4
	$\ell\ell$	7549.1 ± 49.0	6624.6 ± 45.9	5281.4 ± 41.0	3424.4 ± 33.0	2747.7 ± 29.6
	$\tau(\bar{q}_1 q_2)$	35886.8 ± 106.9	14988.7 ± 69.1	290.8 ± 9.6	265.3 ± 9.2	209.5 ± 8.2
	$\tau\tau$	3753.1 ± 34.6	1499.3 ± 21.9	37.9 ± 3.5	26.1 ± 2.9	20.4 ± 2.5
	full-had.	0.0 ± 0.0	0.0 ± 0.0	0.0 ± 0.0	0.0 ± 0.0	0.0 ± 0.0

Table 3.10: Event yield for 1-prong tau decays, for MSSM $t\bar{t} \rightarrow H^\pm W^\mp b\bar{b}$ ($M_{H^\pm}=120$ GeV/c²).

MSSM	<i>1-prong</i>	"W+jets"	$N_{taus(1-prong)} \geq 1$	OS	<i>b-tag</i>
$M_H = 120$ GeV/c ²	$e\tau$	2509.5 ± 28.3	326.1 ± 10.2	315.0 ± 10.0	226.1 ± 8.5
	$\mu\tau$	2702.8 ± 29.3	365.3 ± 10.8	359.5 ± 10.7	260.5 ± 9.1
	$\ell(\bar{q}_1 q_2)$	3711.7 ± 34.4	20.4 ± 2.5	16.9 ± 2.3	11.1 ± 1.9
	$\ell\ell$	2747.7 ± 29.6	8.0 ± 1.6	5.4 ± 1.3	2.9 ± 1.0
	$\tau(\bar{q}_1 q_2)$	209.5 ± 8.2	7.6 ± 1.6	4.1 ± 1.1	2.9 ± 1.0
	$\tau\tau$	20.4 ± 2.5	1.9 ± 0.8	1.6 ± 0.7	1.0 ± 0.6
	full-had.	0.0 ± 0.0	0.0 ± 0.0	0.0 ± 0.0	0.0 ± 0.0

Table 3.11: Event yield for 3-prong tau decays for MSSM $t\bar{t} \rightarrow H^\pm W^\mp b\bar{b}$, assuming $M_{H^\pm}=120$ GeV/c².

MSSM	<i>3-prong</i>	"W+jets"	$N_{taus(3-prongs)} \geq 1$	OS	<i>b-tag</i>
$M_H = 120$ GeV/c ²	$e\tau$	2509.5 ± 28.3	90.8 ± 5.4	84.7 ± 5.2	58.9 ± 4.3
	$\mu\tau$	2702.8 ± 29.3	98.4 ± 5.6	94.6 ± 5.5	68.2 ± 4.7
	$\ell(\bar{q}_1 q_2)$	3711.7 ± 34.4	21.7 ± 2.6	12.4 ± 2.0	6.1 ± 1.4
	$\ell\ell$	2747.7 ± 29.6	3.8 ± 1.1	1.6 ± 0.7	1.3 ± 0.6
	$\tau(\bar{q}_1 q_2)$	209.5 ± 8.2	2.9 ± 1.0	1.6 ± 0.7	0.3 ± 0.3
	$\tau\tau$	20.4 ± 2.5	0.6 ± 0.5	0.6 ± 0.5	0.3 ± 0.3
	full-had.	0.0 ± 0.0	0.0 ± 0.0	0.0 ± 0.0	0.0 ± 0.0

The event yields due to the presence of the MSSM Higgs for different masses are listed in Tabs. 3.12, 3.13 and 3.14, for the "W+jets"-like selection and for 1- and 3-prong tau decays, respectively. Samples including decays from $t\bar{t} \rightarrow H^\pm W^\mp$ and $t\bar{t} \rightarrow H^+ H^-$ are used. As a reference, the SM $t\bar{t} \rightarrow W^+ W^- b\bar{b}$ process is always shown in the first row. The background processes are also shown in the last lines.

Table 3.12: Event yields for different Higgs masses in the "tau-dilepton" channel. Event yield due to SM $t\bar{t}$ is shown for comparison.

Samples		Init	Trigger	$N_{lep} \geq 1$	$N_{jets} \geq 2$	$\cancel{E}_T > 40$ GeV
SM $t\bar{t}$	WW	82800.0 ± 164.0	50720.4 ± 128.3	22875.5 ± 86.2	20358.4 ± 81.3	14912.8 ± 69.6
$M_H = 100$ GeV/ c^2	WH	82800.0 ± 120.5	47612.7 ± 91.4	18441.8 ± 56.9	14837.6 ± 51.0	11743.0 ± 45.4
	HH	82800.0 ± 151.2	44912.4 ± 111.3	13751.1 ± 61.6	10068.5 ± 52.7	7840.1 ± 46.5
$M_H = 120$ GeV/ c^2	WH	82800.0 ± 162.4	47519.9 ± 123.0	19196.2 ± 78.2	14839.0 ± 68.7	11901.5 ± 61.6
	HH	82800.0 ± 162.4	44351.5 ± 118.8	15411.6 ± 70.1	10120.1 ± 56.8	7866.6 ± 50.1
$M_H = 140$ GeV/ c^2	WH	82800.0 ± 124.2	46936.2 ± 93.5	20005.1 ± 61.0	14360.3 ± 51.7	11866.8 ± 47.0
	HH	82800.0 ± 176.5	43269.0 ± 127.6	17066.2 ± 80.1	8688.7 ± 57.2	6888.6 ± 50.9
$M_H = 160$ GeV/ c^2	WH	82800.0 ± 123.9	46405.9 ± 92.8	20891.6 ± 62.3	13157.3 ± 49.4	11274.2 ± 45.7
	HH	82800.0 ± 160.8	42047.7 ± 114.6	19024.6 ± 77.1	5429.2 ± 41.2	4689.0 ± 38.3

Table 3.13: Event yield for 1-prong tau decays for different Higgs masses.

1-prong		"W+jets"	$N_{taus(1\text{-prong})} \geq 1$	OS	$b\text{-tag}$
SM $t\bar{t}$	WW	14912.8 ± 69.6	171.1 ± 7.5	149.0 ± 7.0	107.8 ± 5.9
$M_H = 100$ GeV/ c^2	WH	11743.0 ± 45.4	706.3 ± 11.1	680.9 ± 10.9	628.9 ± 10.5
	HH	7840.1 ± 46.5	723.4 ± 14.1	700.8 ± 13.9	645.3 ± 13.3
$M_H = 120$ GeV/ c^2	WH	11901.5 ± 61.6	729.3 ± 15.2	702.5 ± 15.0	504.4 ± 12.7
	HH	7866.6 ± 50.1	756.3 ± 15.5	735.6 ± 15.3	656.0 ± 14.5
$M_H = 140$ GeV/ c^2	WH	11866.8 ± 47.0	627.5 ± 10.8	605.8 ± 10.6	547.4 ± 10.1
	HH	6888.6 ± 50.9	631.2 ± 15.4	614.2 ± 15.2	529.5 ± 14.1
$M_H = 160$ GeV/ c^2	WH	11274.2 ± 45.7	515.4 ± 9.8	491.2 ± 9.6	432.1 ± 9.0
	HH	4689.0 ± 38.3	361.8 ± 10.6	351.5 ± 10.5	271.8 ± 9.2

Table 3.14: Event yield for 3-prong tau decays for different Higgs masses.

Decays (3-prongs)		"W+jets"	$N_{taus(3\text{-prongs})} \geq 1$	OS	$b\text{-tag}$
SM $t\bar{t}$	WW	14912.8 ± 69.6	104.2 ± 5.8	74.7 ± 4.9	46.8 ± 3.9
$M_H = 100$ GeV/ c^2	WH	11743.0 ± 45.4	219.2 ± 6.2	197.8 ± 5.9	182.7 ± 5.7
	HH	7840.1 ± 46.5	195.4 ± 7.3	180.8 ± 7.1	161.7 ± 6.7
$M_H = 120$ GeV/ c^2	WH	11901.5 ± 61.6	218.1 ± 8.3	195.5 ± 7.9	135.0 ± 6.6
	HH	7866.6 ± 50.1	216.9 ± 8.3	205.1 ± 8.1	186.9 ± 7.7
$M_H = 140$ GeV/ c^2	WH	11866.8 ± 47.0	207.3 ± 6.2	188.0 ± 5.9	167.5 ± 5.6
	HH	6888.6 ± 50.9	197.6 ± 8.6	187.8 ± 8.4	158.4 ± 7.7
$M_H = 160$ GeV/ c^2	WH	11274.2 ± 45.7	178.1 ± 5.8	163.2 ± 5.5	140.5 ± 5.1
	HH	4689.0 ± 38.3	100.9 ± 5.6	95.3 ± 5.5	75.9 ± 4.9

3.5 Kinematical distributions

Kinematical distributions may help to better characterize the samples and distinguish the production mechanism. In particular some distributions may be used to separate signal from background. Distributions are shown for signal (i.e. charged Higgs) and relevant backgrounds. As a reference, the H^+ mass $120 \text{ GeV}/c^2$ is chosen. In the following figures, the red line "Higgs" refers to the process $t\bar{t} \rightarrow W^+ H^- b\bar{b}$ while the black line "ttbar" refers to the SM $t\bar{t}$ decay.

Leptons, jets, and event variables

Lepton (i.e. electron and muon) isolation (calorimeter and tracking), transverse momentum and impact parameter are shown in Fig. 3.2 and Fig. 3.3, respectively. As expected, distributions are similar for Higgs and $t\bar{t}$ events.

Figure 3.2: Tracking (left) and calorimeter (right) isolation for electrons (top) and muons (bottom). Leptons are matched to MC for Higgs and $t\bar{t}$ events.

Figure 3.3: p_T distribution (left) and impact parameter (right) distributions of all leptons (electrons and muons) in Higgs and $t\bar{t}$ events (matched to MC).

Transverse momentum distribution of the b -jets (matched in MC) is shown in Fig. 3.4 for Higgs and $t\bar{t}$ events. The b -jet in $t\bar{t}$ events has a harder p_T spectrum than in Higgs events, due to the kinematical constraint of the Higgs mass value. Distributions of the (leading and next-to-leading) jet p_T are shown in Fig. 3.5; jet multiplicity and MET distributions are shown in Fig. 3.6. Distributions are shown for all events before the given variable is used in the event selection, and are normalized to unity. In the specific case of Fig. 3.4, distributions are calculated using MC matched objects, while the distributions in Fig. 3.5 and Fig. 3.6 do not rely on MC matching.

Figure 3.4: p_T distribution of the b -jets (matched to MC) for Higgs and $t\bar{t}$ events.

Figure 3.5: Transverse momentum distribution for the leading (left) and next-to-leading (right) jets, after the "trigger" and " $N_{lep} \geq 1$ " cuts (no MC matching is used).

Figure 3.6: Jet multiplicity distribution after the " $N_{lep} \geq 1$ " cut (left); MET distribution after the " $N_{jet} \geq 2$ " cut (right). Signal and background events are shown. Distributions are shown before the given variable is used in the selection.

Taus

Tau lepton leading track p_T , sum of the charged tracks p_T in the isolation cone surrounding the tau leading track are shown in Fig. 3.7.

The ratio of the leading track tau p_T and the p_T of the corresponding tau jet may be used as an indication of the polarization of the tau decays [6]:

$$R = \frac{p_T^{track_\tau}}{p_T^{jet_\tau}} \quad (3.4)$$

Figure 3.8 shows the distribution of R for tau leptons in events coming from W boson with respect to the same quantity from charged Higgs decays. Distributions are shown for the tau reconstructed objects before any cut and using MC matching (left), and after the OS cut but no MC matching (right) is applied. The shapes are different at the generation level (left) and are due to the different polarization of the tau lepton in the two cases as W and H bosons have different spin. The R distribution could be used to increase the purity of the final Higgs sample by using the shape as an additional discriminating variable. However, it

appears that after reconstruction and after applying the selection cuts, the difference in the two distributions appears to be minimal.

Figure 3.7: Leading track p_T of the tau reconstructed object (left); Sum of the charged track p_T ($\sum p_T^{iso}$) in the isolation cone ($\Delta R = 0.5$) around the tau's leading track direction (right). Distributions are shown after the MET cut is applied.

Figure 3.8: R distribution (see text) for reconstructed hadronic tau leptons coming from decays of the W and Higgs ($M_{H^\pm} = 120 \text{ GeV}/c^2$) bosons, separately: after matching to MC and before any cut is applied (left), after the OS cut without MC matching (right).

The impact parameter distributions are shown in Fig. 3.9 for electrons/muons and taus.

Figure 3.9: Impact parameter significance (d/σ) of the reconstructed leptons (electrons, muons and taus) after the MET cut is applied.

b -jets and b -tagging

Two b -tagging algorithms are tested: the track counting algorithm [29] and the combined secondary vertex algorithm [27]. The latter algorithm may be used as an additional selection in order to further reduce the number of background events. The use of b -tagging is not used as part of the "default" event selection due to the reduced signal efficiency.

Figure 3.10 shows the average value of the two jets with highest b -discriminant values. The distributions are shown for signal and background events after event reconstruction and after the OS cut is applied. The average distribution is at smaller values for W/Z +jet events where b -jets are not expected.

Figure 3.10: Average b -tagging discriminant value of the two jets with largest b -tag discriminants for signal and background events. Values from the reconstructed jets are shown after the OS cut. A Higgs mass of $M_{H^\pm} = 120 \text{ GeV}/c^2$ is used.

3.6 Branching ratio exclusion limits

The $\text{BR}(t \rightarrow H^+b)$ exclusion limits are estimated using the excess of events in the tau dilepton channel with respect to the expected yield in the SM framework alone.

Figure 3.11 shows the expected number of selected events as a function of the branching ratio $\text{BR}(t \rightarrow Hb)$. Expectations are shown for different $t\bar{t}$ decay channels: $t\bar{t} \rightarrow WWb\bar{b}$ (i.e. WW), $t\bar{t} \rightarrow WHb\bar{b}$ (i.e. WH), $t\bar{t} \rightarrow HHb\bar{b}$ (i.e. HH). A Higgs mass value of $M_{H^\pm} = 120 \text{ GeV}/c^2$ is used. All signal and background contributions are summed together to the red line in Fig. 3.11 (right) and the 95% confidence limit is calculated; systematical uncertainties of 10% are included from [22].

Figure 3.11: Number of events expected in the WW, WH and HH decay channels (left), and the total number of events after full event selection up to the OS cut (right), as a function of the branching ratio $\text{BR}(t \rightarrow H^+b)$ and for a Higgs mass of $M_{H^\pm} = 120 \text{ GeV}/c^2$.

Estimating the limit

The limits on the $\text{BR}(t \rightarrow Hb)$ are set by comparing the number of selected events (N) with the number of selected events expected by the MSSM (N_{exp}) for each $\text{BR}(t \rightarrow H^+b)$.

The MSSM hypothesis is tested using a Poisson distribution with $P(N, N_{exp})$ representing the probability to observe a number of events larger or equal to N when N_{exp} are expected. When $P(N, N_{exp}) > 95\% \text{ C.L.}$ the MSSM hypothesis is rejected and the corresponding BR is excluded. In the determination of the limits, one picks the BR for which the condition $P(N, N_{exp}) = 95\% \text{ C.L.}$ is satisfied. In what follows we assume that the number of selected events (N) is the expected from the SM.

In Fig. 3.11 (right), the horizontal line indicates the number of selected events expected from the SM. The red line, increasing with the branching ratio, gives the number of events (N_{exp}) in the presence of the MSSM Higgs boson for a given mass as a function of $\text{BR}(t \rightarrow H^+b)$. It was estimated [22] that a systematical uncertainty of 10% affects the value of N_{exp} , and this uncertainty is accounted for by repeating the same procedure for the values $N_{exp} = N_{exp} \times (1 - 0.1)$. The intersection of the two lines (including the shaded area for the uncertainties) yields the BR exclusion limits.

Results

After applying the procedure described above (Sec. 3.6), the BR limit values are calculated assuming masses of $M_{H^\pm} = 100, 120, 140$ and $160 \text{ GeV}/c^2$ for the H^\pm boson. Results are shown in Fig. 3.12 (left) as a function of the Higgs mass. Figure 3.12 (right) shows how the exclusion limits for the BR evolve as a function of the integrated luminosity.

Figure 3.12: Left: Exclusion limits on the $BR(t \rightarrow H^\pm b)$ as a function of the Higgs mass, for an integrated luminosity of 200 pb^{-1} . Right: Branching ratio limits estimated for a Higgs mass value $M_{H^\pm} = 120 \text{ GeV}/c^2$, as a function of the integrated luminosity.

3.7 Cut on the track transverse momentum

The track p_T cut on the tau jet is a crucial parameter to increase or reduce the number of signal and background events. The p_T threshold value was varied and the corresponding BR limits have been derived accordingly for the number of signal and background events surviving the full event selection (up to the OS cut). Figure 3.13 shows how the BR limits evolve when different p_T cuts are applied to the tau jets and to the tau leading tracks. The BR limits may be marginally improved by increasing the tau leading track p_T threshold up to $25 \text{ GeV}/c^2$. As a reminder, for this analysis the cuts at $p_T^{jet} > 30 \text{ GeV}/c$ and $p_T^{tau track} > 20 \text{ GeV}/c$ are used.

Figure 3.13: Branching ratio limits as a function of the tau jet p_T cut, for different leading track tau p_T (1-prong only). The limits are estimated with a 3σ including a 10% systematical uncertainty, and for an integrated luminosity of 200 pb^{-1} . A Higgs mass value of $M_{H^\pm} = 120 \text{ GeV}/c^2$ is used.

3.8 Conclusions

The potential for the discovery of the charged Higgs boson in top quark decays, in the tauonic model, is studied. If a light H^\pm boson exists within the MSSM, the CMS experiment is well equipped to discover it in the first few years of operation ($\approx 100 - 200 \text{ pb}^{-1}$). The study has been performed for 200 pb^{-1} of integrated luminosity of proton-proton collisions at $\sqrt{s} = 10 \text{ TeV}$. Results show that similar sensitivity can be reached to that achieved by the Tevatron [15, 7], already with early LHC data ($< 50 \text{ pb}^{-1}$).

Chapter 4

Study at 7 TeV and first results from data

4.1 Analysis approach

The following study focus on the mass range $80 \leq M_{H^\pm} \leq 160 \text{ GeV}/c^2$. The event selection is purposely optimized assuming that the charged Higgs decays always to a tau lepton and neutrino, i.e. $\text{BR}(H^{+-} \rightarrow \tau^+ \nu_\tau) = 1$. Using the chosen event selection it is studied if there is sensitivity to a leptophobic charged Higgs, i.e. $\text{BR}(H^{+-} \rightarrow c\bar{s}) = 1$.

Figure 4.1: Main $t\bar{t}$ decays involving a charged Higgs decaying to a tau lepton and neutrino.

The event selection is optimized from comparing different categories of events. Signal enriched categories (i.e. containing the production of the charged Higgs boson) include hadronic and leptonic tau decays (fig. 4.1). Background dominated categories are used to constraint the systematic errors. A total of twenty

(20) exclusive categories are chosen for this purpose and will be discussed in detail in Section 4.3. The event yields observed in each category are assumed to follow a Poisson distribution. The event yields observed are affected by experimental systematic errors which can be assumed, in first approach, to be Normal distributed with zero mean value and a standard deviation which encodes the corresponding uncertainty. Therefore a likelihood function, L , is built, from product of the Poisson distributions, one per category, and Normal distributions, one per systematic error. The details can be found in [30]. The likelihood is maximized in the unknown parameters: the systematic errors and $\text{BR}(t \rightarrow H^+b)$. A fixed $\text{BR}(t \rightarrow H^+b)$ is excluded at 95% CL when:

$$P\left(\chi_{(1)}^2 < \max_{\text{BRfree}}\{2\log L\} - \max_{\text{BRfixed}}\{2\log L\}\right) = 95\%CL \quad (4.1)$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \max_{\text{BRfree}}\{2\log L\} - \max_{\text{BRfixed}}\{2\log L\} > 3.84$$

$\max_{\text{BRfree}}\{2\log L\} - \max_{\text{BRfixed}}\{2\log L\}$ is the difference between the maximizations of $2\log L$ with the $\text{BR}(t \rightarrow H^+b)$ free and fixed. It is assumed that this difference between maximizations follows a chi-squared distribution with 1 degree of freedom (see [31]).

In the next Section the list of Data and simulation samples used for the analysis is given. The method is applied and discussed in Sections 4.3, 4.4 and 4.5.

4.2 Data and MC samples

$t\bar{t}$ generation in the context of the MSSM was done using the CMS official software. For reference, version 3_5_6 and the global tag MC_3XY_V26 were used for this purpose [32]. The generation of the events was done as follows:

- a standard model $t\bar{t}$ sample generated with Madgraph [17] was used as a starting point. The sample is referenced in CMS by the following dataset: /TTbarJets-madgraph/Summer09-MC_31X_V3_7TeV-v3/GEN.
- the original standard model events were used to generate different decay scenarios corresponding to different H^+ masses and decay modes. We have also only considered $t\bar{t} \rightarrow W^+H^-b\bar{b}$ or $t\bar{t} \rightarrow H^+H^-b\bar{b}$, as by a proper combination of each event type any branching ratio $\text{BR}(t \rightarrow H^+b)$ scenario can be generated.
- as the Madgraph generated events are parton level events, they had to be interfaced also to a PYTHIA6 based hadronizer [33, 34] which took care of evolving the parton showers and the remnants of the proton which constitute the underlying event. The decays of the taus were properly handled by the Tauola package [19]. A fast simulation of the CMS detector was used to obtain the response of the detector to the events [20].

Table 4.1 summarizes the Monte-Carlo based samples used to prepare the 7 TeV study.

In order to validate the procedure just described the control SM $t\bar{t}$ sample was compared with the official CMS $t\bar{t}$ sample. No particular difference was found at the level of the spectra of the reconstructed objects. For the following it is considered a production cross section of 165 pb for $t\bar{t}$ (NNLO) [2].

Table 4.2 lists the background MC based samples considered for the study. These are mainly W, Z and QCD.

CMS data acquired from early 7 TeV proton-proton collisions was also studied. The acquired data is divided in different categories according to the type of trigger which initiated the decision to store an event. There are electron/gamma trigger based datasets, muon trigger based datasets, etc. The overlap between these different sets is non negligible. To avoid the duplication of events when analyzing the data specific trigger bits are reinforced (vetoed) when running on each dataset. All is listed in table 4.3.

For analysis, only quality centrally certified runs were used. In CMS the certification is centrally provided and a list of good runs and luminosity sections are available through the so called JSON files. Runs from 142303 to 144114 were used for the study. Further quality conditions are reinforced such as requiring a good vertex reconstructed and vetoing beam-gas events which often produce a large number of low quality tracks (scrap events) [35].

Technically a different version of the CMS official software with respect to the one used for MC was used to analyze data. CMSSW version 3_6_1 and the detector conditions according to the globaltag START36_V9

Table 4.1: Generated signal MC samples. The dataset path is an internal CMS reference which can be used to access the sample through the Grid for analysis. The samples were all published on the DBS Instance cms_dbs_ph_analysis_02. In the dataset paths WH stands for $t\bar{t} \rightarrow W^+H^-b\bar{b}$, HH for $t\bar{t} \rightarrow H^+H^-b\bar{b}$ and WW for the SM $t\bar{t}$ decay. The numbers correspond to the H^+ mass and HAD stands for the leptophobic decay mode of the charged Higgs.

Dataset path
//TTbarJets-madgraph_7TeV_GEN_5/lpedro4-TTbarJets-madgraph_7TeV_GEN_5-bb0255719a29d1edfa04f59dc7013a43/USER (madgraph events)
//TTbarJets-madgraph_7TeV_GEN_5/pedrom-TTbarJets_WW-madgraph_7TeV-96b953e8a6dc8cee6d32294a0547b484/USER (control sample - SM)
//TTbarJets-madgraph_7TeV_GEN_5/lpedro4-TTbarJets-madgraph_7TeV_HH100-b0e139a443fdbfbaf5825a9485c3eb3e/USER
//TTbarJets-madgraph_7TeV_GEN_5/lpedro4-TTbarJets-madgraph_7TeV_HH100HAD_3-60759ee1fab0bbd3dca1a6c023ffe7f0/USER
//TTbarJets-madgraph_7TeV_GEN_5/lpedro4-TTbarJets-madgraph_7TeV_HH100_2-b0e139a443fdbfbaf5825a9485c3eb3e/USER
//TTbarJets-madgraph_7TeV_GEN_5/lpedro4-TTbarJets-madgraph_7TeV_HH120-7b78ff8518833799eb77ade46bb50b6/USER
//TTbarJets-madgraph_7TeV_GEN_5/lpedro4-TTbarJets-madgraph_7TeV_HH120HAD-bf3f4c7b621f06c0e8898c1a165cf96/USER
//TTbarJets-madgraph_7TeV_GEN_5/lpedro4-TTbarJets-madgraph_7TeV_HH140-9df244707ab7d98396d076626d9a8556/USER
//TTbarJets-madgraph_7TeV_GEN_5/lpedro4-TTbarJets-madgraph_7TeV_HH140HAD-9713c7048c88773f1a88a57398c710bb/USER
//TTbarJets-madgraph_7TeV_GEN_5/lpedro4-TTbarJets-madgraph_7TeV_HH160-c686deb820a2184eb33e41a9ae74bc24/USER
//TTbarJets-madgraph_7TeV_GEN_5/lpedro4-TTbarJets-madgraph_7TeV_HH160HAD-551ddb6aa37d574d82a72fb0c0b52ae86/USER
//TTbarJets-madgraph_7TeV_GEN_5/lpedro4-TTbarJets-madgraph_7TeV_HH80-afcf5de496b945d59687c831f9731dd/USER
//TTbarJets-madgraph_7TeV_GEN_5/lpedro4-TTbarJets-madgraph_7TeV_HH80HAD-9b4c3fd26b99ab69401de89f71f46f5/USER
//TTbarJets-madgraph_7TeV_GEN_5/lpedro4-TTbarJets-madgraph_7TeV_WH100-41bf7b279a1bd15e74ce05ffa9b78836/USER
//TTbarJets-madgraph_7TeV_GEN_5/lpedro4-TTbarJets-madgraph_7TeV_WH100HAD-de3c9016b73c47d63a56a1006851c86f/USER
//TTbarJets-madgraph_7TeV_GEN_5/lpedro4-TTbarJets-madgraph_7TeV_WH120HAD-bc3844a05ad27857ea55f82d8a47268e/USER
//TTbarJets-madgraph_7TeV_GEN_5/pedrom-TTbarJets_WH120-madgraph_7TeV-f5f76ab5df382f44ac739c8c47852d02/USER
//TTbarJets-madgraph_7TeV_GEN_5/lpedro4-TTbarJets-madgraph_7TeV_WH140-b9b47687cfe7fbc4dc5ed8b06c026156/USER
//TTbarJets-madgraph_7TeV_GEN_5/lpedro4-TTbarJets-madgraph_7TeV_WH140HAD-12227aa6961e6062847ac8b6f9c929f4/USER
//TTbarJets-madgraph_7TeV_GEN_5/lpedro4-TTbarJets-madgraph_7TeV_WH160-5ed949353b486bb5048b3437630faf3b/USER
//TTbarJets-madgraph_7TeV_GEN_5/lpedro4-TTbarJets-madgraph_7TeV_WH160HAD-dedd98a8979687572a1da98ba52359/USER
//TTbarJets-madgraph_7TeV_GEN_5/lpedro4-TTbarJets-madgraph_7TeV_WH80-8b42dd82db9d57968a790873cab5c633/USER
//TTbarJets-madgraph_7TeV_GEN_5/lpedro4-TTbarJets-madgraph_7TeV_WH80HAD-309cfe8f56b63d9a1b2a99435cf854ce/USER

Table 4.2: Background MC samples. The dataset path is a internal CMS reference which can be used to access the sample through the Grid for analysis. The LO cross-sections were taken from the official CMS production page [1]. The NLO, NNLO and NNNLO cross-sections were taken from [2].

Z	
//ZJets_M10to50-sherpa/Spring10-START3X_V26_S09-v1/GEN-SIM-RECO	2800pb (NLO)
//ZJets_7TeV-madgraph-tauola/Spring10-START3X_V26-v1/GEN-SIM-RECO	11923.5pb (LO)
W	
//WJets_7TeV-madgraph-tauola/Spring10-START3X_V26-v1/GEN-SIM-RECO	28000pb (NLO)
//SingleTop_sChannel-madgraph/Spring10-START3X_V26_S09-v1/GEN-SIM-RECO	4.6*0.32442pb (NNLO)
//SingleTop_tChannel-madgraph/Spring10-START3X_V26_S09-v1/GEN-SIM-RECO	63*0.32442pb (NLO)
//SingleTop_tWChannel-madgraph/Spring10-START3X_V26_S09-v1/GEN-SIM-RECO	10.6 (NLO)
//VVJets-madgraph/Spring10-START3X_V26_S09-v1/GEN-SIM-RECO	4.8pb (LO)
//VqJets-madgraph/Spring10-START3X_V26_S09-v1/GEN-SIM-RECO	35.8pb (LO)
QCD	
//InclusiveMu15/Spring10-START3X_V26_S09-v1/GEN-SIM-RECO	0.2969e9*2.684e-4pb (LO)
//QCD_EMEnriched_Pt30to80/Spring10-START3X_V26_S09-v1/GEN-SIM-RECO	0.0593e9*0.059pb (LO)
//QCD_EMEnriched_Pt80to170/Spring10-START3X_V26_S09-v3/GEN-SIM-RECO	0.906e6*0.148pb (LO)
//QCD_Pt170/Spring10-START3X_V26_S09-v1/GEN-SIM-RECO	2.547e+4pb (LO)

Table 4.3: Data samples. The dataset path is a internal CMS reference which can be used to access the sample through the Grid for analysis. The rightmost column lists the trigger bits used to run over each sample. Mu/Ele stands for muon/electron based trigger and the number associated to it is the p_T threshold.

Dataset path	Trigger used
/Mu/Run2010A-PromptReco-v4/RECO	HLT_Mu9
/EG/Run2010A-PromptReco-v4/RECO	HLT_Ele15_LW_L1R and not HLT_Mu9
/BTau/Run2010A-PromptReco-v4/RECO	HLT_SingleIsoTau30_Trk5 and not HLT_Ele15_LW_L1R and not HLT_Mu9

were used to reconstruct data. The reconstructed data was further analyzed with version 3_8_1_patch2 and PF2PAT as it also takes care of associating the reconstructed physics objects to a single vertex (reducing the contamination from pileup events) and takes care of removing events for which the Forward Hadronic Calorimeter (HF) had a noisy response. [36, 35] Other misalignment corrections were not applied as at the time this thesis is written a reprocessing of data is taking place in order to take these into account.

In the next Section, data is compared with simulation. Even if data and simulation had to be analyzed with different CMS software versions, due to technical details which are out of scope of this text, the comparison is overall good.

4.3 Event Selection

Trigger

Only the events selected by the electron, muon and tau triggers are considered (HLT_E1e15_LW_L1R OR HLT_Mu9 OR HLT_SingleIsoTau30_Trk5 [23]).

Cuts Definition

e/μ : The e/μ is defined as a PFElectron (PFMuon) with $p_T > 20$ GeV/c and $|\eta| \leq 2.4$, $|d0| < 400 \mu\text{m}$, isolated ($\text{ecaliso} > 0.8$ (0.9), $\text{trackiso} > 0.9$). Additionally, the first e/μ selected in an event must have eidTight (GlobalMuonTight), and $|\eta| \leq 2.4$ (2.1). The second e/μ selected in an event must have the opposite charge of the first.

JetX: PFJet with $p_T > X$ GeV/c and $|\eta| < 2.5$ with at least one associated track. The AK5 jet reconstruction algorithm and all the others PF2PAT defaults are used.

METX: $\cancel{E}_T > X$ GeV (PFMET).

τ : PFTau with $p_T > 20$, $|\eta| \leq 2.4$, leading track $|d0| < 400 \mu\text{m}$, isolated ($\text{isoprongspt} + \text{isogammapt} < 5\%$). The following tauIDs are applied: $\text{leadingTrackFinding}$, leadingPionPtCut , $\text{byIsolationUsingLeadingPion}$, againstMuon , againstElectron [36]. The pseudo-rapidity regions $1.46 < |\eta| < 1.56$, where ECAL Barrel and Endcap calorimeter meet are excluded.

τ_{hard} : τ with $pT_{track} > 20$, $|\text{charge}| = 1, 1$ or 3 prongs. The charge of the tau must have the Opposite Sign of the charge of the selected e/μ (if it was selected).

τ_{soft} : τ with $pT_{track} < 20$, $|\text{charge}| = 1, 1$ or 3 prongs. The charge of the tau must have the Opposite Sign of the charge of the selected e/μ (if it was selected).

τ_{fake} : τ which is neither τ_{hard} nor τ_{soft} .

Jet_Btag : PFJet medium b-tagged $\text{TCHP} > 2$ [37].

ZLike: In the 2 leptons (e/μ) case: the mass of the 2 leptons and the Missing energy transverse to the proton beams axis (\cancel{E}_T) (momentum of \cancel{E}_T along the beam axis is considered zero) is in the interval $[70, 120] \text{GeV}/c^2$, or, if we have 2 electrons or 2 muons, the mass of the 2 leptons is in the $[85, 100] \text{GeV}/c^2$. In the 1 e/μ and 1 tau case: the mass of the lepton, tau and the \cancel{E}_T (momentum of \cancel{E}_T along the beam axis is considered zero) is in the interval $[70, 120] \text{GeV}/c^2$. Additionally, the transverse mass of the lepton and \cancel{E}_T is lower than $40 \text{GeV}/c^2$ (to distinguish from the W decays).

ZVeto: Not ZLike.

Table 4.4: Event yield of the category τ_{hard} of the first plot of figure 4.3

		Trigger	lepton20	Jet30Jet20MET40	tau20	OS.TauTrk20	
$t\bar{t}$	total	379.5 ± 1.0	246.8 ± 0.8	95.2 ± 0.5	56.9 ± 0.4	4.6 ± 0.1	0.5 ± 0.0
Z	total	33864.0 ± 26.9	3556.4 ± 7.3	1815.2 ± 4.1	6.3 ± 0.2	0.2 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.0
W	total	64568.2 ± 20.0	13593.6 ± 9.2	10008.6 ± 7.9	201.8 ± 1.1	3.0 ± 0.1	0.1 ± 0.0
QCD	total	8597276.0 ± 4366.1	2009906.8 ± 2007.6	22590.0 ± 212.0	12.0 ± 3.5	0.0 ± 0.0	0.0 ± 0.0
Total MC	total	8696087.1 ± 4366.3	2027303.4 ± 2007.7	34509.0 ± 212.2	276.9 ± 3.7	7.9 ± 0.2	0.7 ± 0.1
Data	total	26849836.0 ± 5181.7	10097044.0 ± 3177.6	32211.0 ± 179.5	417.0 ± 20.4	11.0 ± 3.3	2.0 ± 1.4

Figure 4.2: Variables used on the ZLike cut. Each histogram is normalized to one. In the following described event selections, Opposite Sign charge is required between the 2 $e/\mu/\tau$. *Up Left*: Transverse mass of the e/μ and MET after the cuts e/μ , MET20 and τ_{hard} . *Up Right*: Mass of the e/μ , τ and MET after the cuts e/μ , MET20 and τ_{hard} . *Down Left*: Mass of the two e/μ after the cuts 2 e/μ and MET20. *Down Right*: Mass of the two e/μ and MET after the cuts 2 e/μ and MET20 τ_{hard} .

The cuts defined above are combined in order to build twenty exclusive categories. The event yields observed in each category are all summarized in figure 4.3. In order to attribute a category to an event we proceed sequentially until the first corresponding category is found. The procedure just described guarantees that no double counting occurs for an event.

Table 4.4 shows the event yield observed for one category. The building of this category is illustrated as follows: after Trigger, one e/μ is required ($p_T > 20$), $\cancel{E}_T > 40$ GeV and two jets (one jet with $p_T > 30$ GeV/c and another with $p_T > 20$ GeV/c), one τ ($p_T > 20$ GeV/c) with a hard track ($p_T > 20$ GeV/c) and Opposite Sign charge with respect to the selected e/μ . The MC presented is simply normalized to the total integrated luminosity acquired, i.e. $2.2 pb^{-1}$ (no systematic uncertainty corrections are considered). The category just described corresponds to the τ_{hard} bin presented in the first plot presented in figure 4.3.

All the event yields observed in figure 4.3 are compared to MC predictions after applying the likelihood maximization which will be described in Section 4.4. In the maximization only SM $t\bar{t}$ is considered, i.e., $\text{BR}(t \rightarrow H^+b)=0$. The MC expected events are stacked in order to sum up the simulation expectations. In this sense in the distributions W stands for W+QCD and the Z stands for Z+W+QCD. The black line, TTbar, represents the SM and the red line, Higgs, represents the tauonic model with $\text{BR}(t \rightarrow H^+b)=0.5$ considering a H^+ mass of $120\text{GeV}/c^2$. The MC integration uncertainties are represented by the vertical bars.

As already noticed, it is expected in the tauonic model that $t\bar{t}$ events where one of the tops decays to a H^+ to have large large \cancel{E}_T (fig. 3.6) and that one of the b-jets is softer than in the SM (fig. 3.4). The categories of the first plot in (fig. 4.3) are purposely indented to be enriched in such events and that is the main justification for the choice of a category with $\cancel{E}_T > 40$ and two jets with different p_T thresholds. The first required e/μ comes from the leptonic decay of the W boson (see figure 4.1).

The tauonic model distinguishes from the SM as it is expected to yield a larger number of events with taus at the cost of a decrease on the number of events with hard e/μ . Notice that the e/μ produced directly in the W decay are p_T harder than those that are produced in the decay of a tau coming from a H^+ or W bosons, due to the emission of two extra neutrinos in the decay of the tau.

When comparing the number of e/μ with the number of taus, the normalization error is restricted. A larger number of taus might be due to an unexpected increase of the tau fake rate or efficiency. The number of fake taus is therefore controlled by the category τ_{fake} . The distinction between τ_{hard} and τ_{soft} ensures further that an eventual excess of true taus will correspond to taus coming from the H^+ . This distinction is based on figure 3.7. In order to restrict the errors on the tau fake rate and efficiency, specific categories are used and shown in the second and third plots. These are fake-enriched categories from W+jets events and real tau-enriched categories from $Z \rightarrow \tau\tau$. The separation between Z and W events is achieved by the ZLike cut defined from figure 4.2.

Finally, the categories of the fourth plot intend to select $t\bar{t}$ events where the W boson decays to quarks (see figure 4.1). Two b-tagged jets are required to reject W and QCD events. Notice that since we are looking to the relation between e/μ and taus, the exclusion limits will be approximately independent of the assumed b-tag uncertainty. The categories of the fifth plot where b-tag is not required are intended to control the mistag efficiencies which contaminate the fourth category which depends on b tagging.

On figure 4.4 the same data and the same categories are shown. The only difference is that the red-line, Higgs, represents the leptophobic model with $\text{BR}(t \rightarrow H^+b)=0.5$. The exclusion limits will be very dependent of the assumed b-tag and $t\bar{t}$ uncertainties. These categories were optimized for the tauonic model.

In the next Section the systematic uncertainties associated to the event selection are described in more detail.

Figure 4.3: Categories of events used for 2.2 pb^{-1} of data. $\text{BR}(H^{+-} \rightarrow \tau^+ \nu_\tau) = 1$ (tauonic model). The event selection used is written in each plot (for instance, the e/μ category of the first plot has the event selection two e/μ , $\text{MET} > 40$ and two jets, one with with $p_T > 30 \text{ GeV}/c$ and another with $p_T > 20 \text{ GeV}/c$).

Figure 4.4: Categories of events used for 2.2 pb^{-1} of data. $\text{BR}(H^+ \rightarrow c\bar{s})=1$ (leptophobic model). The event selection used is written in each plot (for instance, the e/μ category of the first plot has the event selection two e/μ , $\text{MET}>40$ and two jets, one with with $p_T>30 \text{ GeV}/c$ and another with $p_T>20 \text{ GeV}/c$).

4.4 Systematic Uncertainties

The systematic uncertainties associated to the event selection described in the previous section include:

- the overall normalization and the individual cross-sections of the processes $t\bar{t}$, Z, W, and QCD;
- the energy scale of the jets and of the reconstructed MET;
- the efficiency and fake rate for e/μ and tau;
- the efficiency and mistag rates for the b tagging algorithm used.

Table 4.5 summarizes these systematic uncertainties and also the systematic errors obtained from the maximization of the Likelihood function considering the SM hypothesis, i.e. $\text{BR}(t \rightarrow H^+b) = 0$. Each systematic error is assumed to be Normal distributed, with 0 mean value and a standard deviation equal to the assumed systematic uncertainty.

Table 4.5: Table of systematic uncertainties

Description	Systematic uncertainty (assumed)	Systematic error (from $\max_{BR_{fixed}=0}\{2\log L\}$)
Normalization	10%	14%
$t\bar{t}$ cross-section	10%	3.5%
W cross-section	10%	11%
QCD cross-section	20%	-14%
Jets and MET energy scale	10%	5.6%
Tau efficiency	10%	1.5%
Tau fake rate	10%	-1.1%
e/μ fake rate	10%	4.1%
btag efficiency	20%	-12%
btag fake rate	10%	-1.0%
MC integration	MC stat. uncertainty for each category	different for each category

The systematic error on each process cross-section affects the expectation values for each MC sample. This is encoded by multiplying the cross section by $(1 + \text{syst. error})$. Notice that an overall normalization uncertainty is also attributed which corresponds to an overall scale factor related to the luminosity uncertainty.

For the selection efficiencies and fake rates of the physics objects e/μ , tau and b-jet, the errors are considered in a similar way: the systematic error of the efficiency (fake rate) of the selection of a given object affects the MC sample expected values by multiplying the number of events with one true (fake) selected object by $(1 + \text{syst. error})$.

Jet and MET energy scale change the MC expectations with a slightly different factor. To evaluate it, an energy scale factor, $X = 1.1$, is used to multiply the jets and MET energy scale. After applying the standard event selection N_X events are observed. Then $\frac{N_X - N_1}{N_1} \left(1 + \frac{\text{syst. error}}{X - 1} \right)$ is the factor which is used to re-scale the expected MC event yields due to the variation of the Jets and MET scale.

The MC samples are summed only after each mentioned correction is applied to each sample. Then, each category will have a MC prediction with an associated error from the MC integration. The MC predictions are assumed to be Normal distributed, the mean value is the MC prediction and the standard deviation is the associated error. The maximization on the MC true predictions is done analytically. The maximization on the other parameters is done numerically.

The choice of the uncertainties are justified below:

- the uncertainties in the Z cross-section and integrated luminosity are accounted in the Normalization error. The Z and W cross-section and integrated luminosity uncertainties were based on [38];
- the uncertainty on the $t\bar{t}$ cross-section was based on the several cross-sections obtained by different methods presented in [2];
- the efficiency and fake-rate as well as the QCD cross-section uncertainties were based on the available comparisons between data and Monte Carlo published on the notes [38, 40, 41, 42, 39];
- the e/μ efficiency error can be accounted by proper combinations of the other errors. It was verified that for the chosen categories the results don't change by introducing it.

4.5 BR limits: Results and projections

In figure 4.12, on the left, the black dots represent the obtained $\text{BR}(t- > H^+b)$ exclusion limits from data for each H^+ mass. The blue expected band was obtained using one thousand pseudo-experiments where the number of events in each category follows a Poisson distribution with mean number given by the MC predictions. The MC predictions are obtained from the $\max_{\text{BRfixed}=0}\{2\log L\}$ on data. The blue band is the band where lay the obtained $\text{BR}(t- > H^+b)$ exclusion limits of 95% of the pseudo-experiments. The fact that the black dots are inside the blue band means that the obtained exclusion limits are inside of what one would expect to obtain if the $\text{BR}(t- > H^+b)=0$ (SM).

In the figure 4.7, on the left, the black thick line represent the expected $\text{BR}(t- > H^+b)$ exclusion limits for each H^+ mass if data equals the MC predictions with all the systematic errors set to zero and $\text{BR}(t- > H^+b)=0$ (SM). The black thin line represent the expected $\text{BR}(t- > H^+b)$ exclusion limits for each H^+ mass if data equals the MC predictions with $\text{BR}(t- > H^+b)=0$ (SM) and no systematic uncertainties are considered. The blue expected band was obtained using one thousand pseudo-experiments where the number of events in each category follows a Poisson distribution with mean number given by the MC predictions with all the systematic errors set to zero and $\text{BR}(t- > H^+b)=0$ (SM). The blue band is the band where lay the obtained $\text{BR}(t- > H^+b)$ exclusion limits of 95% of the pseudo-experiments.

The statistical Confidence Level in figure 4.12 was obtained using one thousand pseudo-experiments where the number of events in each category follows a Poisson distribution with mean number given by the MC predictions. The MC predictions are obtained for the MC integration errors set to zero, the $\text{BR}(t- > H^+b)=\text{BRlimit}$ (the exclusion limit) and the other systematic errors from the $\max_{\text{BRfixed}=0}\{2\log L\}$ on data. The statistical Confidence Level corresponds to the fraction of pseudo-experiments with $\max_{\text{BRfixed}=\text{BRlimit}}\{2\log L\} - \max_{\text{BRfree}}\{2\log L\} < 3.84$ (see eq. 4.2).

The statistical Confidence Level is not the full Confidence Level, because the variation is done only on the Poisson distributions, not also on the Normal distributions of the systematic errors. Because the systematic uncertainties are only accurate up to the order of magnitude, saying that we have 90% CL or 95% CL, when the variation is done on the systematic errors, is pretty much the same thing. But a statistical Confidence Level of 95% tells us that if the real $\text{BR}(t- > H^+b)=\text{BRlimit}$, then in 100 CMS-data collections of 2.2pb^{-1} (or other considered integrated luminosity) in 95 we will not reject the real $\text{BR}(t- > H^+b)$.

The p-value of the fit in figure 4.12 was obtained using one thousand pseudo-experiments where the number of events in each category follows a Poisson distribution with mean number given by the MC predictions. The MC predictions are obtained from the $\max_{\text{BRfree}}\{2\log L\}$ on data (λ). The p-value corresponds to the fraction of pseudo-experiments with $\max_{\text{BRfree}}\{2\log L\} < \lambda$, i. e. with a Likelihood lower than the Likelihood of data. This number is expected to be high because we are only varying in each pseudo-experiment the Poisson values, not the systematics which are taken from the data fit and will partially absorb the statistical fluctuation in data. If this number is low (e.g. less than 10%) it will mean that MC plus the considered systematics cannot describe well enough the data.

Results for $2.2pb^{-1}$

Figure 4.5: *Left:* BR limits for the tauonic model with $2.2pb^{-1}$ of data. *Right:* The statistical CL, obtained from Poisson fluctuation on each category, is $\sim 95\%$. *Bottom:* The model (MC plus uncertainties) agrees with data within statistics.

Figure 4.6: *Left:* BR limits for the leptophobic model with 2.2pb^{-1} of data. *Right:* The statistical CL, obtained from Poisson fluctuation on each category, is $\sim 95\%$. *Bottom:* The model (MC plus uncertainties) agrees with data within statistics.

Projections for $2pb^{-1}$

Figure 4.7: *Left*: Expected BR limits for the tauonic model with $2pb^{-1}$ of integrated luminosity. *Right*: The statistical CL, obtained from Poisson fluctuation on each category, is $\sim 95\%$.

Figure 4.8: *Left*: Expected BR limits for the leptophobic model with $2pb^{-1}$ of integrated luminosity. *Right*: The statistical CL, obtained from Poisson fluctuation on each category, is $\sim 95\%$.

Projections for $10pb^{-1}$

Figure 4.9: *Left*: Expected BR limits for the tauonic model with $10pb^{-1}$ of integrated luminosity. *Right*: The statistical CL, obtained from Poisson fluctuation on each category, is $\sim 95\%$.

Figure 4.10: *Left*: Expected BR limits for the leptophobic model with $10pb^{-1}$ of integrated luminosity. *Right*: The statistical CL, obtained from Poisson fluctuation on each category, is $\sim 95\%$.

Projections for $100pb^{-1}$

Figure 4.11: *Left*: Expected BR limits for the tauonic model with $100pb^{-1}$ of integrated luminosity. *Right*: The statistical CL, obtained from Poisson fluctuation on each category, is $> 95\%$.

Figure 4.12: *Left*: Expected BR limits for the leptophobic model with $100pb^{-1}$ of integrated luminosity. *Right*: The statistical CL, obtained from Poisson fluctuation on each category, is $> 95\%$.

4.6 Conclusions

The first results for the $\text{BR}(t \rightarrow H^+b)$ exclusion limits are obtained with 2.2pb^{-1} of CMS data in both tauonic and leptophobic models. Projections show that similar sensitivity can be reached to that achieved by the Tevatron [15, 7], already with early data ($> 10\text{pb}^{-1}$).

The exclusion limits for the leptophobic model are very dependent of the assumed uncertainties. These categories were optimized for the tauonic model. With more time one can define a different set of categories optimized to produce results for the leptophobic model.

For the tauonic model, there is the possibility to define e/μ_{hard} and e/μ_{soft} categories in order to use the lepton p_T spectrum, which is different for leptons coming from taus and W bosons decays, to improve the exclusion limits. In order to achieve this, one should use leptons with p_T lower than $20\text{ GeV}/c$.

As integrated luminosity increases, more categories can be defined in order to restrict even more the systematic errors. Also, more studies of the background, from the top, Electroweak and QCD groups, will be available and more accurate systematic uncertainties can be assumed. CMSSW is a huge piece of code and there will be errors that will become apparent and will be corrected as more data becomes available.

There are several ways to account for the systematic uncertainties and none is perfect. There are two types of systematic errors: the real errors (faults) that can be avoided and the systematic uncertainties (e.g. coming from the limited knowledge of the value of some constants) [43]. The only correct way of dealing with the faults is by detecting and correcting them.

The method used here to account for the systematic uncertainties is a good one because when using a sufficient number of well chosen categories:

- one can restrict the systematic errors producing a result that is almost independent of the values of the assumed systematic uncertainties;
- one guaranties that the effect of the faults is lower than the statistical error as long as the p-value of the maximization is high enough.

The last advantage is very important because it will show us us whether there is the need for background from data estimation. Although not needed, the use of background from data estimation can improve the results on categories where the MC predictions have a large integration error.

Chapter 5

Conclusions and Perspectives

The first $\text{BR}(t \rightarrow H^+b)$ exclusion limits were obtained, from $2pb^{-1}$ of LHC data. The values for H^+ masses between 80 and 160 GeV/c^2 are around 45% for the tauonic model and 25% for the leptophobic model. Projections show that the current Branching Ratio exclusion limits, from Tevatron, may be improved with around $10pb^{-1}$ of data.

Until we reach the $10pb^{-1}$, a lot of work needs to be done. The methods used must be discussed within the LIP, Higgs and ParticleFlow CMS groups and lots of tests need to be performed, due to the fact that it will be an early data result.

However, some important goals were already achieved:

- there was an investment in developing tools that explore the capabilities of CMSSW, Grid, the LIP Tier2 and local farm (not discussed here) that allow one to do fast tests on considerable amounts of data and Monte Carlo Simulation.

- there was also an investment in doing the Monte Carlo Simulation at LIP. Methods to keep only the necessary information, maintaining the files within the CMSSW format were developed. There is today at LIP the necessary know-how to ensure that no study will be delayed waiting for a new official Monte Carlo event generation.

- a very general and flexible statistical method that allows one to set discovery and exclusion limits, has well as, if wanted, obtain cross-sections was studied and successfully implemented.

- the work described here enhanced the status of LIP within the Higgs group.

The achieved goals allow one to perspective that the LIP-CMS group is well equipped to successfully contribute to the CMS collaboration data analyses, in this case of the Higgs group.

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